

D6.4 Final Report on the Project Impact

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About this document

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ARIADNEplus partners

ADS	Archaeology Data Service, University of York, United Kingdom
AIAC	Associazione Internazionale di Archeologia Classica, Italy
AMZ	Arheoloski muzej u Zagrebu / Archaeological Museum of Zagreb, Croatia
ARUP-CAS	Archeologický ústav AV ČR, Praha, v.v.i. / Institute of Archaeology of the Academy of Science, Czech Republic
ASU	Arizona State University, Center for Digital Antiquity, United States
ATHENA-RC	Athena Research and Innovation Center, Institute for the Management of Information Systems, Greece
AU	Aarhus University, School of Culture and Society - Department of Archeology and Heritage Studies, Denmark
BUP	Bruxelles Urbanisme & Patrimoine, Direction des Monuments et Sites, Belgium
CARARE	Connecting Archaeology and Architecture in Europe, Ireland
CENIEH	National Research Centre on Human Evolution, Spain
CNR-ISTI	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto di Scienza e Tecnologie della Informazione, Italy
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS), TGIR Huma-Num, France
CONICET	Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET), Instituto de Antropología de Córdoba - IDACOR, Argentina
CYI-STARC	The Cyprus Institute, Science & Technology in Archaeology Research Center, Cyprus
DANS	Data Archiving and Networked Services, Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences, Netherlands
DGPC	Directorate-General for Cultural Heritage, Portugal
FI	Fornleifastofnun Islands, Institute of Archaeology, Iceland
FORTH-ICS	Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas, Institute of Computer Science, Greece
HNM	Hungarian National Museum, Hungary
IAA	Israel Antiquities Authority, Archaeological Division, Israel
IAMP	Institutul de Arheologie Vasile Parvan, Romania
ICA	Istituto Centrale per l'Archeologia (Institute under the Ministry of Culture), Italy
ICCU	Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo Unico (Institute under the Ministry of Culture), Italy
INFN	Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare, INFN-Sezione di Firenze, INFN-Cultural Heritage NETWORK, Italy

INP	Institutul Național al Patrimoniului / National Heritage Institute of Romania, Museum and Archaeological Documentation Department, Romania
INRAP	Institut National des Recherches Archéologiques Préventives, France
KHM-UO	Museum of Cultural History, University of Oslo, Norway
LNEC	Laboratorio Nacional de Engenharia Civil, Portugal
NARA	NARA National Research Institute for Cultural Properties, Japan
NIAM-BAS	National Institute of Archaeology with Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria
ÖAW ACDH-CH	Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften, Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage, Austria
PIN	PIN Soc.Cons.A.R.L. - Servizi Didattici e Scientifici per l'Università di Firenze s.c.r.l., Italy
PP	University of Patras, Department of Cultural Heritage Management and New Technologies, Greece
RGK	Römisch-Germanische Kommission des Deutschen Archäologischen Instituts, Germany
RUG	University of Groningen, Groningen Institute of Archaeology, Netherlands
SND	Swedish National Data Service, University of Gothenburg, Sweden
SRFG	Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft, Austria
UB	Universitat de Barcelona, Departamento de Historia y Arqueología, Spain
UH	University of Helsinki, Department of Cultures, Finland
UniRoma1	Sapienza Università di Roma, Dipartimento di Biologia Ambientale, Italy
USW	University of South Wales, School of Computing and Mathematics, Hypermedia Research Group, United Kingdom
ZRC-SAZU	Scientific Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Institut of Archaeology, Slovenia

Associate partners

BIAA	The British School at Ankara, Turkey
BSA	The British School at Athens, Greece
CENSUS	Census of Antique Works of Art and Architecture Known in the Renaissance, hosted by Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Germany
CISA	Centro Interdipartimentale di Servizi di Archeologia (Università di Napoli L'Orientale)
DataARC	Enabling Research on the Long-Term Human Ecodynamics of the North Atlantic, North Atlantic Biocultural Organization (NABO)
DPCH	Directorate for Protection of Cultural Heritage, North Macedonia
EFA	École française d'Athènes, Greece
IAZ	Institute of Archaeology in Zagreb, Croatia
MBSR	Monuments Board of the Slovak Republic, Slovakia
IsoArch	Isotope database bioarchaeological samples
MISANU	Mathematical Institute of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Serbia
ROCEEH	The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans, Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities, Germany
TAKIN	Takin.Solutions Ltd., Bulgaria
Thanados	The Anthropological and Archaeological Database of Sepultures, hosted by the Natural History Museum in Vienna, Austria
UCL-DIS	University College London, Department of Information Studies, UK
UI-DA	University of Innsbruck, Department of Archaeologies, Austria
UM-AU	University of Minho, Archaeology Unit, Portugal

1 Executive Summary

1.1 ARIADNEplus in brief

The overall objective of the ARIADNE initiative is to help the archaeological research and data management communities in Europe and beyond to more effectively share and use data which are dispersed and often difficult to discover and access.

For this purpose, the initiative has developed a digital infrastructure and services that enable aggregation, integration, and search and retrieval of data records which describe and link to available data. The original ARIADNE project¹ implemented the first e-Infrastructure services for this, ARIADNEplus enhanced these services and provides additional e-research services. The whole e-Infrastructure has been moved to a Cloud-based platform.

The ARIADNE project had 23 partners while ARIADNEplus has a consortium of 41 partners, including from the United States, Argentina, Israel and Japan. Still growing, ARIADNEplus already has 17 associate partners, and there are more collaborations, including in the first place ARIADNEplus' "sister project" Saving European Archaeology from a Digital Dark Age - SEADDA (EU COST Action) for digital repositories. The collaborative work in the ARIADNE network is based on a great sense of shared purpose.

ARIADNEplus integrates data resources from many more archaeological domains and methods than the original ARIADNE project, with now over 3.3 million records in the Data Portal. The aggregated data records have been transformed to Linked Data, which enables novel ways to search, explore and access the data. Indeed, the ARIADNE Data Portal has been turned into an effective research tool.

Thus ARIADNEplus has taken the next steps in enabling data sharing, integration and (re)use for archaeological research across institutional and national, as well as disciplinary boundaries. Fostering a culture of data sharing and joint capacity building will also be crucial for the further success of the ARIADNE initiative.

The non-profit association ARIADNE RI AISBL has been established to direct and manage the further development of the ARIADNE research infrastructure, services and data resources.

1.2 Framework of the impact evaluation

This ARIADNEplus deliverable is the "Final Report on the Project Impact" completed in the last month of the project's lifecycle. The evaluation of the project results covers all activities of the project.

ARIADNEplus is an Integrating Activity funded under the Horizon 2020 Work Programme 2018-2020 for European Research Infrastructures, including e-Infrastructures, henceforth short: RI Programme. An Integrating Activity has to implement three lines of activities, Networking, Transnational and virtual access, and Joint research activities.

A common evaluation scheme for the impact of Integrating Activities does not exist, but ARIADNEplus developed a reporting framework that takes full account of the statements of expected impacts of the RI Programme and/or its section "Specific features for Research Infrastructures", Part D.

¹ ARIADNE (02/2013-1/2017), <http://legacy.ariadne-infrastructure.eu>

Chapter 2 comprises the summarised results of 11 areas of project activities, stated or implied by the expressed expectations of the RI Programme:

- Extension of the stakeholder community
- Supporting the FAIR data agenda in archaeology
- Standardisation of archaeological datasets
- Access to integrated knowledge-based resources
- New services and virtual research environments (VREs)
- Research infrastructures coordination
- Cross-disciplinary fertilisation and sharing of resources
- Innovation and partnership with industry
- Use of services beyond research
- TNA, training activities and resources
- Dissemination and communication

These activities have different weights, for example, *Access to integrated knowledge-based resources* comprises the whole ARIADNEplus Data Portal and integrated datasets, while *Use of services beyond research* is not a project priority, but nevertheless has been one of its ambitions.

Chapter 3 outlines the framework. It describes in greater detail the Integrating Activity scheme, gives important background for the expected impact statements, briefly discusses the 10 statements, and references the sections which present the related activities and results achieved.

1.3 Selected high-level facts & figures

We note some selected high-level facts & figures:

- The ARIADNEplus project started in January 2019 with a consortium of 41 partners, up from 23 of the original ARIADNE project, now comprising 37 partners from 23 European countries and one each from the United States, Argentina, Israel and Japan.
- Thus, the ARIADNE initiative is present more strongly across Europe and in other world regions as well. The inclusion of data from international partners in the ARIADNE Data Portal demonstrates that the initiative has the objective and capacity to expand its data pool beyond Europe.
- Increasingly, there are requests by organisations to join the ARIADNE network as associate partner based on a cooperation agreement: 17 European organisations have already joined the network, extending further ARIADNE's coverage both geographically and thematically.
- The leading role of the ARIADNE initiative as integrator of archaeological data and driving the FAIR data agenda in the sector is confirmed by its recognition by the main institutions for archaeology in Europe, the European Archaeological Council (EAC) and the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA). Former and current presidents of both sit on the ARIADNEplus Scientific Advisory Board.
- The promotion of FAIR data by ARIADNEplus takes different forms, including dissemination of guidance, a FAIR data management plan (DMP) tool and templates for archaeologists, FAIR as part of training activities and resources, and sessions and presentations at domain conferences.
- The new ARIADNE Data Portal provides access to over 3.3 million data records from 31 publishers; some additional datasets are already prepared and will be integrated in early 2023.

- The statistics for the new Data Portal start from January 2021: From January to November 2021 there was a total of 7,165 visitors to the portal. By 9 December 2022, this had increased to 32,000 visitors, an increase of 350%.

2 Summary report of results

This chapter presents the summarised results of the 11 areas of project activity.

Extension of the stakeholder community

> Refers to RI Programme expected impact statement [6].

Growing ARIADNE network of partners

The ARIADNEplus project started in January 2019 with a consortium of 41 partners, up from 23 of the original ARIADNE project, including also partners from the United States, Argentina, Israel and Japan.

Thus, the ARIADNE initiative is now present more strongly across Europe and in other world regions as well. The inclusion of data from the international partners in the ARIADNE data portal demonstrates that the initiative has the objective and capacity to expand its data pool beyond Europe.

Most of the archaeological partners of ARIADNEplus also participate in the COST Action SEADDA (Saving European Archaeology from a Digital Dark Age), a partnership with representation from nearly all European countries, not only those in the EU.

SEADDA and ARIADNEplus have complementary goals. SEADDA is focussed on ensuring a more sustainable future for digital archaeological resources through the creation of new and better repositories, while ARIADNEplus supports finding and accessing data that is being shared through existing and new repositories.

ARIADNEplus increasingly receives requests by organisations to join the ARIADNE network as associate partner based on a cooperation agreement: 17 European organisations have already joined the network, including heritage authorities, archaeological institutes, as well as domain research and technology centres.

These associates strengthen the presence of ARIADNE in some countries, Austria, Bulgaria, Greece, Portugal and the United Kingdom, and expand it to Croatia, North Macedonia, Serbia, Slovak Republic and Turkey.

Through associate projects, the ARIADNE network also expands thematically, e.g., through the ROCEEH project in the field of paleoanthropology in regions of Africa, the Levant, Eurasia and Europe; through DataARC of the North Atlantic Biocultural Organization (NABO) in the research field of long-term human ecodynamics.

Benefits perceived by associate partners

Associate partners are not funded from the ARIADNEplus project budget, but have invested significant time and staff resource in their contributions, particularly those who prepared data for aggregation and integration in the ARIADNE portal; this has also been done by other providers who have not joined as associate partners. It is estimated that through their unpaid effort, ARIADNEplus has leveraged at least an additional 24 person months of work on data provision.

Associate partners perceived impacts regarding institutional policies and capacity building, particularly partners in countries where there has been little previous tradition of open access to research data in archaeology and heritage, i.e., countries in central and south-eastern Europe.

European schools abroad, including the French and British schools based in Athens and Ankara, have been keen to participate. These schools often lack IT resources but sit on massive archaeological legacy

archives. Therefore, they appreciated ARIADNEplus as an opportunity for digital capacity building, networking and sharing of their data.

That many organisations have wanted to join ARIADNEplus as associate partner, and been willing to commit time and resources to it, clearly bodes well for the sustainability of the ARIADNE initiative beyond the existing funded project.

Recognition by major archaeological bodies

The value and impact of the ARIADNE initiative is confirmed by its growth and recognition by the main bodies for archaeology in Europe. The initiative is being recognised by the European Archaeological Council (EAC) and the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA) as the leading integrator of archaeological data resources in Europe and beyond. Former and current presidents of both institutions sit on the ARIADNEplus Scientific Advisory Board, ensuring regular dialogue with both organisations.

ARIADNEplus supports vital interests of these institutions in increasing access to archaeological data through provision of data management guidance and tools, conference sessions with a focus on FAIR and open access data, promotion of digital repositories, and data discovery and access.

Understanding and serving community needs

The development of the ARIADNE research infrastructure, portal and other services is based on a solid understanding of the community needs captured in surveys, focus groups and studies (e.g., the study on the impact of COVID-19).

The ARIADNE research infrastructure clearly supports community needs for services enabling data sharing, discovery and access. The results of the community needs survey in 2019, with responses of 484 researchers and data managers from all partner countries and others included in the analysis, confirmed high appreciation of the ARIADNE data services. The community also welcomes guidance from ARIADNEplus in the application of the FAIR data principles in archaeology.

The ARIADNE/plus surveys in 2013 and 2019 are the only existing large surveys on data practices of archaeologists in Europe. Consequently, results are often referenced by researchers to explain developments in digital archaeology and to underpin arguments.

The survey of archaeological repositories in 2021, with participation of 60 repositories of research centres and heritage agencies, provides an evaluation of the extent to which their current data policies and practices conform to ideals of FAIR and open access data. The recommendations given on how to promote further progress in this regard can inform related measures by major bodies such as the European Archaeological Council (EAC), national heritage agencies as well as research institutions.

Focus group meetings have been held with archaeological professionals and heritage managers (e.g., contract archaeologists, heritage administrators, curators of sites and museums), who are not core intended users of the ARIADNE research data infrastructure. The participants liked the ARIADNE portal and found the search facilities to be user-friendly, and asked how easy it is to upload data to the system.

Participants commented that its value for heritage management depends largely on the availability of data for their country or region, and that contract archaeologists are more likely to use national systems (in the national language) and less likely to need data from across country boundaries. Participants also thought that ARIADNEplus has the potential to inspire new system developments, for example, regarding the structuring and standardisation of systems of heritage management institutions.

Results of the study on the impact of COVID-19 on archaeology and cultural heritage indicated more interest by archaeological researchers to exploit already existing fieldwork reports and data. The

repository survey confirmed this as 24 of the 27 repositories which analyse data access reported an increase ranging from 5% to over 100%. For researchers and repository managers who want to extract information from large numbers of fieldwork reports, ARIADNEplus offers Cloud-based Natural Language Processing (NLP) services.

During the COVID-19 crisis, archaeologists also used online platforms to carry out research tasks, for example virtual support by subject experts of local groups of field archaeologists. ARIADNEplus provides virtual research environment (VRE) services for different tasks and data types.

The COVID-19 crisis showed that many cultural heritage institutions still need to extend their online offer with advanced visual content. Here, the ARIADNEplus Visual Media Service (VMS) for 3D models and Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI) allow exploring heritage sites and objects in engaging ways. The VMS has been presented to heritage institutions and supporting businesses to collect their interest and requirements for using the service.

Supporting the FAIR data agenda in archaeology

> Refers to RI Programme section “Specific features for Research Infrastructures”, Part D, (i) Networking Activities.

Promoting the FAIR data agenda in archaeology

ARIADNEplus is committed to promoting the FAIR data agenda in the archaeological sector in Europe (and beyond), in line with the respective policies of the European Commission and EU member states on open access to publicly funded research data.

The Board of the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA) endorsed the FAIR principles and proposed a collaboration with ARIADNEplus for their implementation in archaeology. The European Archaeological Council (EAC) works with SEADDA, the “sister project” of ARIADNEplus, on progressing the FAIR data agenda in the sector.

The promotion of FAIR data by ARIADNEplus takes different forms, including recommendations and dissemination of guidance, a FAIR data management plan (DMP) tool and templates for archaeologists, FAIR as part of training activities and resources, and sessions and presentations at domain conferences.

FAIR guidance and DMP tool

Researchers and data managers in archaeology look for practical guidance on what is meant by FAIR data and how to create and make it available. For broad dissemination in the sector, ARIADNEplus adopted the PARTHENOS FAIRify guide, which is relevant for both researchers and repositories and available in nine language versions. At present, the unique downloads of the FAIRify guide from the Zenodo repository amount to 3,681 while in June 2021 the unique downloads stood at 2,462, an increase of 49.5%.

ARIADNEplus promotes the standardisation of Data Management Plans (DMPs) and appropriate practices of archaeological researchers and projects, taking account of requirements and standards for archaeological datasets. The ARIADNEplus DMP tool and templates have been developed specifically for archaeologists and conform to European Commission and Science Europe guidelines.

By using the tool, researchers can understand better the requirements for FAIR data and save a lot of time in drawing up a fit for purpose DMP. An online workshop on the DMP tool and templates in March 2022 was attended by 89 participants. Users of the DMP tool have prepared 92 DMPs so far.

Standardisation of archaeological datasets

> Refers to RI Programme expected impact statement [8].

Standardisation based on CIDOC CRM

ARIADNEplus promotes standardisation and integration of archaeological datasets based on the ISO standard CIDOC CRM (Conceptual Reference Model) and domain-specific CRM extensions. Such extensions have been developed by ARIADNE experts, e.g., CRMarcheo (excavations), CRMba (heritage buildings) and CRMtex (e.g., inscriptions, marks, graffiti). These CRM extensions are increasingly being adopted for archaeological research projects and databases, particularly CRMarcheo and CRMba.

More importantly, the ARIADNE initiative not only provides CRM extensions but also FORTH-ICS's 3M (Mapping Memory Manager) system, the most advanced tool for mapping datasets to the CRM and its extensions or application profiles. The system can be accessed and used in the ARIADNEplus D4Science space.

Data catalogue and deeper data integration

The data catalogue developed in the original ARIADNE project (ACDM) initiated the CRM-based standardisation of data catalogues in archaeology, cultural heritage and related fields of the humanities. Based on the jointly developed expertise, the new ARIADNE data catalogue model (AO-Cat) provides greater flexibility and detail to describe data collections as well as individual items.

Deeper integration of domain-specific datasets has been progressed by ARIADNEplus through the creation and testing of CRM-based application profiles, e.g., for ancient texts such as epigraphy and mortuary archaeology. The published application profiles can inspire also other projects which want to use CRM-based profiles for the integration of domain datasets.

Applying core domain vocabularies

A major part of the standardisation work of the ARIADNE initiative in the field of archaeology is demonstrating the power of using common vocabularies for data integration. The core examples here are the Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) and the PeriodO gazetteer for cultural period definitions.

For the subjects of their data resources partners make semantic mappings of terms of "local" vocabularies (thesauri, term lists) to concepts of the large and multilingual Getty AAT. This enables subjects-based searches on the ARIADNE data portal across the integrated data collections and records. In ARIADNEplus, the total number of mappings (in different languages) to the AAT amounts to nearly 21,500 of at present 30 partners, up from over 6,400 of 12 partners in the original ARIADNE project.

For the mapping, ARIADNEplus provides the browser-based interactive Vocabulary Matching Tool on the D4Science platform. Other data interoperability initiatives where providers use different vocabularies can benefit from using this freely available service.

The PeriodO gazetteer system provides unique identifiers (URIs) for cultural periods (including time-ranges) which allow stable linking of archaeological, ancient world and historical data resources which refer to the same period. Started in the original ARIADNE project with the largest contribution of 663 periods for 24 European countries, the collection has been extended by ARIADNEplus partners and associates to 1,880 periods in more European and other countries, e.g., Argentina and Japan.

Through the PeriodO system other institutions and projects can also use the periods mobilised by ARIADNE/plus, enabling wider interlinking of data which relate to the same periods.

Using and sharing Linked Open Data

Data records aggregated in the ARIADNE data portal are transformed to Linked Data which support searching and visualising results within the portal. The Linked Open Data (LOD) knowledge graph of over 175 million RDF triples can also be explored programmatically, using SPARQL queries.

The semantic graph database (GraphDB) can be accessed by researchers and developers through the ARIADNEplus_Lab, which provides a user guide and a set of tools for exploring and analysing the LOD and possibly interlink it with other data.

Increasing the “FAIRness” of archaeological data

The data standardisation promoted by ARIADNEplus increases the overall “FAIRness” of archaeological data. The FAIR principles include as requirements that (meta)data should meet domain relevant community standards (i.e., CIDOC CRM), be described with accurate and relevant attributes (i.e., Getty AAT terms), and encoded using a formal, shared and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation (i.e., W3C RDF for Linked Data). The FAIR principles also include that the (meta)data should be registered in a searchable resource, i.e., the ARIADNE data portal.

Access to integrated knowledge-based resources

> Refers to RI Programme expected impact statement [8].

The new ARIADNE Data Portal exploits the enhanced integration of knowledge-based data resources, i.e., resources described with the CRM-based data catalogue model (AO-Cat) and vocabularies of the domain of knowledge. The portal services are provided freely and openly to all users.

Integrated data records

At the close of the original ARIADNE project in January 2017, 16 data publishers had provided over 1.9 million data records to the portal. Meanwhile, the new portal provides access to over 3.3 million records from 31 publishers integrated based on the new AO-Cat data model. Some additional datasets are already prepared and will be aggregated in early 2023.

Portal access statistics

The statistics for the new data portal start from January 2021: From January to November 2021 there was a total of 7,165 visitors to the portal. By 9 December 2022, this had increased to 32,000 visitors, an increase of 350%.

The top 10 countries from which visitors come to the portal are United Kingdom, United States, France, Bulgaria, Italy, Germany, Netherlands, Hungary, Cyprus, Australia. All, except Australia have data records in the portal. The visitor rates for the top countries have continued to increase for the last year.

Enhanced search facilities

In ARIADNEplus the portal has been enhanced in several ways to offer advanced data search, visualisation and exploration facilities.

The portal now provides multi-lingual and granular subjects search, which builds on the mapping of the “local” vocabularies of partners and associates to the Getty AAT. The Map-search facility offers many new features, including different layer types, heat maps and cluster points for results, polygon support for areas of interest, but also bounding boxes to mask precise location.

Various options for filtering data records can be applied to results of both the Map-search and Timeline-search facility. Furthermore, where available, images of artefacts are included in served data records.

Results of the community needs survey have been duly considered, for example, with the extra effort invested on the Map-search facility to support users' high interest in location-based search of data resources.

The portal as an effective research tool

In ARIADNEplus the data portal has been turned into an effective research tool. Use of different search filters of the portal allows new types of research, for example to explore and compare patterns of settlements or of artefacts found in different regions relating to different cultural periods.

Such research was not possible to achieve so effectively before. It reduces the researchers' effort to discover, combine and analyse data for comparative research.

Use of the portal software beyond ARIADNEplus

Archaeology Data Service (ADS) have decided to adopt the ARIADNE portal system for the primary ADS user interface to their collections. The portal system will also be used in the large-scale "Unpath'd Waters" project which will aggregate marine heritage data from UK waters.

New services and virtual research environments (VREs)

> Refers to RI Programme expected impact statement [2].

Enhanced and new research services

While the Data Portal already provides an effective research tool, ARIADNEplus also enhanced e-research services developed in the original ARIADNE project and added new ones to the portfolio of services and VREs.

Natural Language Processing (NLP) services originally developed in ARIADNE have been enhanced and applied to documents in additional European languages.

A service for subject annotations of archaeological texts with terms of different vocabularies has been developed in response to a need for such annotations in interdisciplinary research projects.

Services for the visualisation and annotation of images and 3D models have been enhanced, including the Digital Autoptic Process (DAP) service for annotations in a CIDOC CRM compliant way of archaeological objects which contain textual or symbolic information, and EpHEMERA for 3D documentation of archaeological sites. Functionalities of these services have been included in the Visual Media Service (VMS).

The original ARIADNE VMS already allowed users effective publication, rendering and exploration of enhanced images (e.g., Reflectance Transformation Imaging - RTI) and high-quality 3D models of buildings and artefacts. In ARIADNEplus the VMS has been enhanced in several respects of which the most important advance is enabling users to link information to selected parts of a 3D model. A visual wizard is included which guides VMS users to easily add such hotspots and interactive links to the related documentation.

Virtual Research Environments (VREs)

Virtual Research Environments (VREs) are one of the most ambitious innovation goals of ARIADNEplus in the field of archaeological research. VREs combine and tailor services for research tasks and data of research communities.

In ARIADNEplus Cloud-based VRE services implemented on the D4Science platform are intended to support research tasks beyond what the data portal already allows. Use of some of the services, especially the Geoserver and Visual Media Service, has been explored in pilots for innovative applications.

To kick-start the VRE development, three use cases workshop were organised which focused on thematic domains represented in ARIADNEplus, including Geospatial, Environmental, Mortuary and ancient DNA data and research. Developers of dataARC and Thanados, which thereafter became associate partners of ARIADNEplus, were among the external participants. In the workshops some needs of researchers were identified and addressed by developing or enhancing VRE services.

The *ARIADNEplus_Lab VRE* offers researchers a set of tools to process, visualise and analyse ARIADNE as well as own data. The tools include JupyterHub (pre-installed and ready to use), RStudio and the DataMiner analytics engine to specify and execute data computing tasks on the D4Science Cloud-based infrastructure.

The virtual research lab also provides researchers access to the *ARIADNEplus Linked Open Data (LOD)* in the semantic graph database (GraphDB) and tools for exploring the LOD with an available web GUI or programmatically, using SPARQL queries.

The previously mentioned new service for subject annotations of archaeological texts with terms of different vocabularies has been added to the *ARIADNEplus_Lab VRE*.

VREs have also been developed building on the Cloud-based Geoserver. A major development is the National Geoportal for Archaeology in Italy, which will provide map-based access to data from archaeological fieldwork. Use of the Geoserver has also been explored in a pilot VRE for research on the Esquiline area of Rome.

Enhancements of the *Visual Media Service (VMS)*, particularly capability to add to 3D models hotspots and interactive links to documentation, have turned it into a research environment. It is also relevant for other purposes, e.g., museum information about cultural artefacts in 3D.

Finally, it is worth highlighting that research tools which are available online in Cloud-based environments allow researchers to avoid investing effort to acquire, implement, maintain and upgrade them. Instead of dealing with IT issues, the researchers can focus on their research questions and collaboration.

Research infrastructures coordination

> Refers to RI Programme expected impact statement [3]

Coordination with related e-Infrastructures

Coordination with related e-Infrastructures in the field of humanities and heritage research started in the original ARIADNE project through networking with the major European projects already active at that time. These are CENDARI (e-Infrastructure for historical archives), CLARIN (language resources and tools), DARIAH (arts & humanities tools, methods, training), and Europeana.

Among the common topics with Europeana developer groups are the growing importance of 3D content, use of Cloud-based solutions, and the adoption of the FAIR principles by cultural heritage institutions. An additional important topic is common approaches for connecting different user groups with archaeological content resources.

Close relations exist with the E-RIHS research infrastructure for heritage science, as several partners were already involved in the preparatory phase of this ESFRI Roadmap initiative. Particularly relevant for ARIADNEplus are scientific data from advanced methods of material analyses and conservation of artefacts. As some ARIADNEplus partners employ such methods, the CIDOC CRM application profile CRMhs (heritage science) has been created, which can also be used for the E-RIHS DIGILAB component.

The first showcase implementation of the CRMhs profile will be the new scientific data repository of ARIADNEplus partner INFN, which is currently being developed. INFN datasets based on the general CIDOC CRM based ARIADNE catalogue model are already included in the data portal.

ARIADNEplus has also close ties with the Competence Centre on the Conservation of Cultural Heritage project (4CH, coordinated by INFN) which develops a virtual competence centre using a Cloud-based ICT infrastructure to provide services and support to cultural heritage institutions.

Connecting with EOSC

Today, the main common point of coordination between research infrastructures, particularly their e-Infrastructure component, is the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative.

Therefore, ARIADNEplus prepared registering its portfolio of Cloud-based services in the EOSC Marketplace (catalogue of resources). This will allow other research e-Infrastructures in the EOSC ecosystem use complementary ARIADNEplus services relevant for their operation, and *vice versa*.

Some Cloud-based services provided by CNR-ISTI for ARIADNEplus through the D4Science platform can already be found in the EOSC Marketplace. However, in June 2022 EOSC released the Resource Data Model to production which is to be used for research IT services.

A mapping of the services part of the ARIADNE catalogue model (AO-Cat) to the EOSC Resource Data Model has been created, so that services described in the ARIADNE catalogue are discoverable along with services of e-Infrastructures of other communities federated by EOSC.

It is also worth noting that a platform-level integration of the D4Science platform with the EOSC exists which allows connecting the ARIADNEplus part of D4Science in a transparent way with the EOSC (e.g., through federated identity services).

The ARIADNE initiative also aims to support the ambitious goals of the recently launched European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) initiative. The ex-ante impact assessment of the ECCCH recognised ARIADNEplus as an important related research infrastructure, enabling to reach the archaeological domain, and providing essential insights into what is needed for FAIR cultural heritage data.

Cross-disciplinary fertilisation and sharing of resources

> Refers to RI Programme expected impact statement [6].

In the ARIADNE research e-Infrastructure initiative, cross-disciplinary fertilisation is being promoted by the participation of research groups and sharing of datasets from different fields of archaeological research, which has been greatly extended by ARIADNEplus.

Cross-fertilisation is particularly being fostered by the common objective of research groups to share and integrate data to enable comparative and interdisciplinary research, which ARIADNEplus supports through advancing the semantic interoperability of data resources.

CIDOC CRM application profiles, with a common CRM core and extensions for datasets of different archaeological domains, could play an important role in future cross-disciplinary research. In ARIADNEplus the work on such application profiles has significantly contributed to building common understanding and cross-fertilisation. Different and common aspects of domain datasets became clearer in the process.

Cross-fertilisation has also been fostered between scholars and developers of e-research services in the ARIADNEplus VRE use cases workshops. VREs must be co-designed by scholars and technical experts. In the process, service developers learn about the requirements of scholars' projects, and scholars learn how VREs can support their research tasks.

Collaboration and cross-fertilisation with external developers is enabled based on the ARIADNEplus Linked Open Data (LOD) which is accessible through a dedicated VRE. The ARIADNEplus_Lab VRE provides tools for exploring and building on the LOD, i.e., link it with data of other projects.

Innovation and partnership with industry

> Refers to RI Programme expected impact statement [4].

In archaeology, private sector commercial actors are businesses of contract archaeologists and consultancies which provide professional services for developers and heritage management agencies in preventive archaeology.

Archaeological businesses, often spin-offs or otherwise related to archaeological research centres, can benefit from using ARIADNEplus services and datasets, but may also share fieldwork reports through underlying repositories. Such sharing must be promoted by national or regional authorities and implemented in their data management system or mandated repositories, as in the case of ADS in the UK and DANS in the Netherlands.

In ARIADNEplus innovation in this field focused on using Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies to extract information from fieldwork reports for metadata which can be used to enhance access to such reports. Building on the foundational work in the original ARIADNE project and an EOSCpilot project, further development in ARIADNEplus focused on improving the Cloud-based NLP solution and applying it to extract data from fieldwork reports of INRAP in French.

The Cloud-based Visual Media Service (VMS) is considered equally as relevant for cultural heritage institutions and businesses for producing high-quality 3D models and other imagery for museums and heritage sites. The CNR-ISTI VCLab team and ICCU have presented the advanced VMS in a webinar to businesses and heritage institutions to explore existing demand and requirements for using the service.

Among the perceived “selling points” of the VMS are confidentiality, support of high-resolution interactive media, and the capability to link descriptive and narrative text to highlighted parts of a 3D model.

Use of services beyond research

> Refers to RI Programme expected impact statement [9].

ARIADNEplus integrates information on metal-detector and other finds by amateurs in countries where this is permitted, and registration of finds in national databases has been enabled. Therefore, such amateurs are a very relevant user group of the ARIADNE portal.

By bringing records from the finds databases into the ARIADNEplus portal, contributions of citizens to archaeology become visible also at the European level. In turn, such “citizen scientists” can use the portal to look for comparable finds or use it to investigate distribution patterns of finds.

Other groups likely to be interested in learning about archaeological sites and artefacts and actively use the data portal have been considered, particularly teachers and students. For this target group, teaching and learning materials are usually required to promote and support projects in schools or extracurricular activities. However, production of such materials, necessary in different languages, was not possible in the current phase of the ARIADNE initiative.

TNA, training activities and materials

> Refers to RI Programme expected impact statement [5].

Transnational Access (TNA)

The TNA programme enabled researchers and data managers to visit ARIADNEplus competence centres for individual study and training or participation in a summer school at a centre. The themes offered by the three centres were “Data Stewardship” at ADS, “Mapping existing datasets to CIDOC

CRM” at PIN, “Implementing Interoperability” and “Visual Media for the Documentation of Fieldwork and Artefacts” at CNR-ISTI.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic the TNA programme could not be implemented as planned. From the first call only 2 of 13 beneficiaries were able to complete their TNA prior to the travel restrictions. Due to continued insecurity no further calls were issued in 2020 and 2021.

The TNA programme was resumed in 2022, with all training offered as four summer schools between May and July 2022, with 32 participants in total.

Training workshops

Partners reported 12 larger training workshops with a total of 476 participants. The main topics were open access publications and data, FAIR data principles, data management plans, data sharing and interoperability. Eight of the workshops had international and four national participants. Eight of these workshops were organised by partners, and four partners contributed substantially to the programme.

Training Hub

The Training Hub, launched in January 2021, is a content-rich site of training resources selected specifically for archaeological researchers and data managers. The topics were chosen to support the perceived training needs of the ARIADNEplus user community. Across the nine topics, the Hub comprises of 65 Web-accessible resources in English from different providers, ARIADNEplus partners, as well as others. In the period between January 2021 to November 2022, the Hub attracted 3,948 visitors, for a total of 11,586 pages viewed. The Hub has quite a high percentage of return visitors (27.3%).

Dissemination and communication

> Refers to RI Programme expected impact statement [6].

Publications

Since project start in January 2019, partners and associates have published 53 ARIADNEplus related academic publications in journals, conference proceedings, edited volumes, etc. Of these, 45 have been published open access or a preprint version is available in an open access repository.

The publications include the 17 chapters of the open access book “The ARIADNE Impact” (Richards & Niccolucci 2019), published by Archeolingua. Since 7 October 2019, there were 1,590 unique downloads of the book from the Zenodo repository.

Two special issues of open access ARIADNEplus papers are already planned for 2023, the first in *Internet Archaeology*, the second in Spanish in the *Revista del Museo de Antropología*, Argentina. The aim of this special issue is to disseminate the knowledge acquired by ARIADNEplus in Latin America.

Conferences and other events

The ARIADNEplus partners and associates reported 88 conference sessions and other events which they have (co-)organised (42) or attended to give ARIADNE-related presentations and network with participants. Training workshops are not included here.

The total number of reported attendants of the presentations is 4,077, an average of 46 per event. 61 events had international participants, and 27 national participants. Due to the COVID-19 crisis most events were held online.

Project website and Twitter

The ARIADNEplus website informs visitors about the project’s goals, community network, workshops, training and TNA, news & events. In the period between January 2019 to November 2022, the website

attracted about 30,000 visitors, with a total of over 86,000 pages viewed. There has been a steady rate of visitors, between 500-1000 per month, with around 14% being return visitors.

The project's Twitter channel has been used regularly to bring attention to project activities and results; in the last year, the project sent 34 Tweets which received a total of 73,177 views. The channel was reactivated at the end of January 2019 with 900 followers of the original ARIADNE project. Until the beginning of December 2022, the number of followers has grown to nearly 2,100.

3 Framework of the impact evaluation

This chapter describes the reference framework of the ARIADNEplus impact evaluation. The framework is largely determined by the fact that the project has been funded as an Integrating Activity project under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Work Programme 2018-2020 for European Research Infrastructures, including e-Infrastructures.

The Integrating Activity scheme of the Work Programme prescribes that projects have to carry out a defined set of activities according to the Integrated Infrastructures Initiatives (I3) Model: Networking activities, Transnational Access (in-person or virtual) service activities, and Joint Research activities. On top of these are 10 statements of the Work Programme on "Expected Impacts" which such projects should aim to achieve by carrying out the set of I3-Model activities defined in the project and approved with the grant agreement.

The sections that follow describe the Integrating Activity scheme in greater detail, give some important background for the "Expected Impacts" statements, and briefly comment the 10 statements. More background and explanation is given in the sections on the results for the different impacts expected by the Work Programme.

3.1 ARIADNEplus as an Integrating Activity

ARIADNEplus is an Integrating Activity funded under the Horizon 2020 Work Programme 2018-2020 for European Research Infrastructures, including e-Infrastructures (European Commission 2020), henceforth short: RI Programme.

The project is an Integrating Activity for Advanced Communities (INFRAIA-01-2018-2019), where "Advanced" means that the original ARIADNE project (until January 2017) moved the field of Archaeology in Europe from a "Starting" to an Advanced Community, "*whose research infrastructures show an advanced degree of coordination and networking*" (European Commission 2020: 43).

Particularly important to note is the RI Programme's requirement that "*an Integrating Activity shall combine, in a closely co-ordinated manner:*

(i) **Networking activities**, to foster a culture of co-operation between research infrastructures, scientific communities, industries and other stakeholders as appropriate, and to help develop a more efficient and attractive European Research Area;

(ii) **Trans-national access or virtual access activities**, to support scientific communities in their access to the identified key research infrastructures;

(iii) **Joint research activities**, to improve, in quality and/or quantity, the integrated services provided at European level by the infrastructures.

All three categories of activities are mandatory as synergistic effects are expected from these different components" (European Commission 2020: 44, emphasis added).

The combination of these three components of activities is called the Integrated Infrastructures Initiatives (I3) Model, and a section of the RI Programme defines further "Specific features for Research Infrastructures" for Integrating Activities (European Commission 2020: 113-117).

The ARIADNEplus project has been set up following the I3 Model, hence it combines Networking activities, Transnational and virtual access activities, and Joint research activities. The evaluation of the project's impact takes account of the fact that these activities are mandatory and therefore their results should be reported.

It is worth noting that there is no established common framework for the evaluation of the impact of Integrating Activities and comparison between them. Such a framework does not exist, despite the fact that a large number of projects have been funded, e.g., about 90 continued and new ones, including the original ARIADNE project, across all disciplines under the 7th Framework Programme. The reason seems to be that significant differences of the projects with regard to disciplines, types of research infrastructures and user communities do not allow the application of a common evaluation framework.

3.2 RI Programme expected impacts

The main reference for the evaluation of impacts of the ARIADNEplus project is the list of impacts expected from Integrating Activities for Advanced Communities funded RI Programme. In addition, regarding specific activities, the RI Programme section “Specific features for Research Infrastructures – Part D: Integrating Activities” is taken account of (European Commission 2020).

3.2.1 Background for the expected impacts

The RI Programme states 10 expected impacts which are listed below with brief comments. More background is given in the sections on the results for the different impacts expected by the RI Programme. Indeed, some of the statements require a significant amount of background information to be considered appropriately.

This is because the RI Programme statements do not distinguish between different types of research infrastructures which the programme funds, e.g., between natural science laboratories and an e-Infrastructure for research such as ARIADNEplus. Although the statements are meant for all RI types, some tend to have physical research facilities in mind, hence need to be interpreted and specified for digital or e-Infrastructure.

Furthermore, the expectation statements have not been updated to take account of the new research policies for FAIR data and the European Open Science Cloud, although these are mentioned in the section “Specific Features for Research Infrastructures” (and many other parts of the RI Programme).

However, the “Specific Features” section, under Part (i) Networking Activities, includes the suggestion that activities could focus on *“definition of data management plans to organise the efficient curation, preservation and provision of access to data collected or produced under the project, in line with the FAIR principles”*; under Part (iii) Joint Research Activities the document demands, *“Digital services developed under the joint research activities should be exposed under the EOSC catalogue”*. Indeed, at the current stage of development of the FAIR data agenda and the EOSC initiative, these activities must of course be carried out.

3.2.2 Commented list of RI Programme impact expectations

This section addresses the RI Programme’s list of 10 statements of expected impacts, given below in bold italics. For each statement brief comments are given on the implied activities, followed by where in this report these are covered and the initial impact results reported:

[1] *Researchers will have wider, simplified, and more efficient access to the best research infrastructures they require to conduct their research, irrespective of location. They benefit from an increased focus on user needs.*

- These statements essentially concern the ARIADNEplus data portal which integrates datasets from the underlying research infrastructures such as national or institutional repositories. Wider,

simpler and more efficient access to the datasets is enabled by the portal through data discovery and access across all repositories and databases. In addition, other new and advanced RI services have been developed which are addressed under [2].

- For both, the ARIADNEplus data portal and these services, activities have been carried out to understand and support the particular needs of the users. Regarding the data portal, the further development based on identified priority needs has turned the portal from a data discovery into an effective research tool which exploits the integrated rich metadata of the connected data repositories.
- Related activities and results are covered in the following sections:
 - Access to integrated knowledge-based resources ([Section 4.4](#))
 - Understanding and supporting community needs ([Section 4.1.4](#))

[2] *New or more advanced research infrastructure services, enabling leading-edge or multi-disciplinary research, are made available to a wider user community.*

- This statement concerns the development and provision of new and advanced ARIADNEplus data services and virtual research environments (VREs).
- Related activities and results are covered in the following sections:
 - Enhanced and new research services ([Section 4.5.2](#))
 - VRE use cases and development ([Section 4.5.3](#))

[3] *Operators of related infrastructures develop synergies and complementary capabilities, leading to improved and harmonised services. There is less duplication of services, leading to an improved use of resources across Europe. Economies of scale and saving of resources are also realised due to common development and the optimisation of operations.*

- This statement concerns the contribution of the project to the coordinated development of major e-Infrastructures for digital humanities, cultural heritage content, heritage science (e.g., material studies and conservation), and ARIADNEplus for archaeology.
- A major focus of the coordination activities has been the development and alignment of data catalogues. Furthermore, joint activities, for instance, focused on common goals such as the implementation of the FAIR data principles or particular data objects such as 3D models.
- Meanwhile, however, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) has become the core initiative for enabling the goals mentioned in the RI Programme statement (i.e., synergies between RIs services, saving of resources through sharing, economies of scale).
- Related activities and results are covered in the following sections:
 - Research infrastructures coordination ([Section 4.6](#))
 - Standardisation of archaeological datasets ([Section 4.3](#))

[4] *Innovation is fostered through a reinforced partnership of research organisations with industry.*

- For the area of archaeology this statement concerns archaeological businesses which carry out fieldwork in preventive or so-called developer-led archaeology. Furthermore, services for cultural and creative businesses could be relevant.
- Related activities and results are covered in the following section:
 - Innovation and partnership with industry ([Section 4.8](#))

[5] A new generation of researchers is educated that is ready to optimally exploit all the essential tools for their research.

- This statement concerns the training opportunities offered by the project, which include Transnational Access (TNA) to ARIADNEplus competence centres, training courses and resources. The training offer of course includes guidance on the application of the FAIR data principles, and tools to develop FAIR data management plans (DMP) for archaeological data.
- Related activities and results are covered in the following sections:
 - Supporting the FAIR data agenda in archaeology ([Section 4.2](#))
 - TNA, training workshops and resources ([Section 4.10](#))

[6] Closer interactions between a larger number of researchers active in and around a number of infrastructures facilitate cross-disciplinary fertilisations and a wider sharing of information, knowledge and technologies across fields and between academia and industry.

- This statement concerns the cross-disciplinary fertilisations promoted by the ARIADNE e-Infrastructure initiative through involving research groups and sharing of datasets from different fields of archaeological research. ARIADNEplus extends the cross-fertilisation potential further by incorporating many more archaeological research communities and types of data.
- Under the category “industry”, the project mainly considers archaeological businesses and cultural and creative businesses.
- Related activities and results are covered in the following sections:
 - Extension of the stakeholder community ([Section 4.1](#))
 - Cross-disciplinary fertilisation and sharing of resources ([Section 4.7](#))
 - Innovation and partnership with industry ([Section 4.8](#))
 - Dissemination and communication ([Section 4.11](#))

[7] For communities which have received three or more grants in the past, the sustainability of the integrated research infrastructure services they provide at European level is improved.

- Not applicable – Explanation: The archaeological research community so far has been supported twice by Integrating Activity grants, for ARIADNE and ARIADNEplus. Nevertheless, the ARIADNE initiative of course strives to sustain the implemented RI services at the European level beyond the ARIADNEplus project.

[8] The integration of major scientific equipment or sets of instruments and of knowledge-based resources (collections, archives, structured scientific information, data infrastructures, etc.) leads to a better management of the continuous flow of data collected or produced by these facilities and resources.

- This statement essentially concerns the work of ARIADNEplus on the aggregation of datasets of digital archives and collections and their integration for search and access through the data portal. This aggregation and integration requires the application of data description standards so that the resources actually become knowledge-based, i.e., based on established ontologies and terminology of the domain of knowledge (archaeology, cultural heritage). Such standardisation is also a key requirement for making datasets FAIR.
- Related activities and results are covered in the following sections:
 - Supporting the FAIR data agenda in archaeology ([Section 4.2](#))

- Standardisation of archaeological datasets (*Section 4.3*)
- Access to integrated knowledge-based resources (*Section 4.4*)

[9] *When applicable, the integrated and harmonised access to resources at European level can facilitate the use beyond research and contribute to evidence-based policy making.*

- The main intended user groups of the ARIADNEplus data access services are archaeological researchers and data managers. Going beyond research, professionals in preventive archaeology and cultural heritage administrators and practitioners are relevant user groups. A particular use case beyond research is also metal-detector and other finds by amateurs described in established national databases from which ARIADNEplus aggregates information (descriptions, images).
- However, ARIADNEplus provides free and open access to the online services of the research infrastructure. Therefore anybody interested can access and use the services and data resources, although for virtual research environments (VREs) services on the D4Science platform this may require registration.
- Contributions to evidence-based policy making by researchers who use ARIADNEplus services and data may be possible, but this has not been defined as a core focus of the ARIADNE initiative in its current phase.
- Related activities and results are covered in the following section:
 - Use of services beyond research (*Section 4.9*)

[10] *When applicable, the socio-economic impact of past investments in research infrastructures from the European Structural and Investment Funds is enhanced.*

- Not applicable – Explanation: The RI Programme considers socio-economic impact only related to research infrastructures which have been built with (co-)investment from the European Structural and Investment Funds, which does not apply for ARIADNE or underlying digital repositories or databases. It concerns large physical facilities, e.g., laboratories and research instruments, in fields such as energy, materials or life sciences research, often with related companies for industrial innovation and development. Such research infrastructures should demonstrate significant socio-economic impacts in the region, i.e., contribute to employment, economic prosperity and growth.

4 Full report of the impact results

This chapter describes in detail the work and results in 11 areas of project activities. Its parts are structured as follows: the first section addresses the RI Programme expected impact and the general approach of the project for the related activities. This is followed by sections which describe the activities carried out and results achieved. Each part also includes a brief summary of the results. These summaries are brought together in the summary report (*Chapter 2*).

4.1 Extension of the stakeholder community

4.1.1 Expectation and project approach

RI Programme expectation

The list of statements on expected impacts of the RI Programme does not include an explicit statement on the extension of the stakeholder community. However, building a community and promoting interaction between different organisations, researchers and data managers is essential for the impact of a research infrastructure.

This is acknowledged by the expected impact statement [6] *“Closer interactions between a larger number of researchers active in and around a number of infrastructures facilitate cross-disciplinary fertilisations and a wider sharing of information, knowledge and technologies across fields and between academia and industry.”*

The statement recognises the importance of sharing resources by the different stakeholders involved by research infrastructures. For e-Infrastructures like ARIADNEplus, this is indeed essential to expand the pool of knowledge-based data resources, drive adoption of the RI services, and maintain the data-centred and other services. A broad stakeholder community is also necessary to ensure the sustainability of the research infrastructure services.

The section “Specific features for Research Infrastructures” of the RI Programme, Part D, (i) Networking Activities, suggests activities aimed to grow and jointly manage data resources, for instance, *“joint management of access provision and pooling of distributed resources”* and *“development and maintenance of common databases for the purpose of networking and management of the users and infrastructures”*.

Actually, these suggested Networking activities are organisational and technical, while stakeholders first need to be committed to share knowledge-based data resources or support other project activities, such as promotion of FAIR good practices, for instance.

Project approach

In January 2019, ARIADNEplus started with a consortium of 41 partners² while the initial ARIADNE project had 23 partners. The consortium now comprises 37 formal partners from 23 European countries and one each from the United States, Argentina, Israel and Japan. These are the Arizona State University (Center for Digital Antiquity, tDAR repository) in the United States, the Instituto de Antropología de Córdoba (CONICET-IDACOR) in Argentina, the Israel Antiquities Authority, and the National Research Institute for Cultural Properties (NARA) in Japan. Thus, the ARIADNE initiative is present now not only more strongly across Europe but also in other world regions.

² ARIADNEplus partners, <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/partners/>

Special attention regarding other stakeholders is being devoted to the coordination with major archaeological agencies and associations, e.g., European Archaeological Council, European Association of Archaeologists, CAA International, and others; new institutional associate partners with a regional focus (e.g., central and south-eastern Europe) and associate projects with a thematic focus.

ARIADNEplus is being recognised by archaeological institutions and projects as leading the development of research data infrastructure and services for the sector. Therefore, ARIADNEplus increasingly receives requests to join the ARIADNE network as associate partner or project.

4.1.2 High-level recognition and support

In the first round of the ARIADNE initiative, the core institutions of both the archaeological domain and the research infrastructures domain in Europe already acknowledged ARIADNE's leading role in building infrastructure and services for sharing and accessing archaeological data.

The **European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)** in their Roadmap 2016 acknowledged ARIADNE's role as the leading integrator of archaeological research data infrastructures: *"In the archaeological sciences the ARIADNE network developed out of the vital need to develop infrastructures for the management and integration of archaeological data at a European level. As a digital infrastructure for archaeological research ARIADNE brings together and integrates existing archaeological research data infrastructures so that researchers can use the various distributed datasets and technologies"* (ESFRI 2016: 175).

From the perspective of archaeology, the **European Archaeological Council (EAC)**³ strongly encouraged organizations to participate in the ARIADNE initiative. The EAC is comprised of heads of national bodies responsible under law for the management of the archaeological heritage in the Council of Europe member states. In their Amersfoort Agenda, setting the agenda for the future of archaeological heritage management in Europe, the Council emphasises *"the need to share, connect and provide access to archaeological information with the help of digital technologies. The key to this aspiration is to improve collaboration – we need to share rather than exchange. It is essential to encourage the development of European data-sharing networks and projects in the field of archaeology. The ARIADNE project is an excellent European initiative in this regard and participation in this project should be strongly encouraged"* (Schut et al. 2015: 21).

In 2021, at the 10th Plenary Session of the Council of Europe's Steering Committee for Culture, Heritage and Landscape (CDCPP), the then EAC President Barney Sloane highlighted ARIADNEplus' role for *"pooling of shared knowledge, rapid access, re-use for research and conservation"* and *"serving Europe's archaeological information to the world"* (Sloane 2021).

Representation of the EAC and EAA in the ARIADNEplus Scientific Advisory Board

The recognition of ARIADNE as the leading integrator of archaeological data resources in Europe is confirmed by the participation of presidents of both the European Archaeological Council (EAC) and the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA)⁴ in the ARIADNEplus Scientific Advisory Board.

Since 2019, the EAC has been represented by Leonard de Wit, Past President and Honorary Member of the EAC Board, while the current President is Ann Degraeve, Head of Department of Archaeological Heritage in Brussels, an ARIADNEplus partner organisation; the EAA, from 2019, has been represented by Felipe Criado Boado, now Past President, and since 2021 also Eszter Bánffy, the current President of the EAA. Since 2013, Professor Bánffy has been Director of the Romano-Germanic Commission at the German Archaeological Institute which participates in ARIADNEplus.

³ European Archaeological Council (EAC), <https://www.europae-archaeologiae-consilium.org>

⁴ European Association of Archaeologists (EAA), <https://www.e-a-a.org>

This ensures a regular dialogue with both organisations, for example the EAA Board has proposed a collaboration with ARIADNEplus for the implementation of the FAIR principles in archaeology. For the same purpose, the EAC Board involves the SEADDA network (see below), which includes all ARIADNEplus archaeological partners.

ARIADNEplus supports vital interests of these institutions through conference sessions with a focus on FAIR and open access data at the EAA and other conferences, FAIR data guidance ([Section 4.2.3](#)), the data management plan (DMP) tool and templates ([Section 4.2.4](#)), the survey of archaeological repositories (in [Section 4.1.4](#)), and of course the data aggregation, discovery and access services.

4.1.3 Growing the ARIADNEplus community

The ARIADNEplus network extends globally and works with many organisations and initiatives whose aims vary widely. Some are focussed on the provision of specialised services, others have geographical or thematic remits. Several of the project partners are members of and/or involved with these organisations, fostering collaboration and communication across the network. This section covers the growth of the ARIADNEplus initiative through associate institutions and projects. Cooperation with ongoing European research infrastructure projects and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative is addressed in [Section 4.6](#).

ARIADNEplus and SEADDA

SEADDA (Saving European Archaeology from a Digital Dark Age)⁵ is a COST Action aimed to foster the development of archaeological data repositories in countries where the research community lacks appropriate repositories. Such repositories require specialist knowledge and mechanisms which ensure that the archaeological data will be openly available for re-use by future generations of researchers.

SEADDA brings together archaeologists and data management specialists to share expertise, provide knowledge and training in matters of data archiving and access. The activities address the lack of persistent and open access repositories in many European countries, which also hampers participation in research collaboration.

SEADDA is being led by ARIADNEplus partner Archaeology Data Service (ADS) and several other partners are members of the project consortium, with representation from nearly all European countries, not only those in the EU. ARIADNEplus and SEADDA have complementary goals. SEADDA fosters the development of FAIR archaeological data repositories, while ARIADNEplus supports finding and accessing data that is being shared through existing and new repositories.

ARIADNEplus Associate partners

Offering organisations to become an ARIADNEplus Associate partner has been very successful, as 17 institutions and projects have already joined the network⁶. Associate partners sign a cooperation agreement with ARIADNEplus confirms their interest in progressing shared goals and joint activities, which can take various forms, e.g., data preparation and aggregation, participation in thematic working groups, cooperation on training activities, development of tools.

It is worth noting that seven of the cooperation agreements signed with the original ARIADNE project led to major institutions becoming formal partners of ARIADNEplus: archaeology and cultural heritage institutions in the European countries of Denmark, Iceland, Norway, Portugal and Spain joined the

⁵ SEADDA - Saving European Archaeology from the Digital Dark Age (COST Action), <https://www.seadda.eu>

⁶ ARIADNEplus: Our network, <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/our-network/>

project, and from other countries, the Israel Antiquities Authority and the Digital Antiquity consortium at Arizona State University, which hosts their digital repository tDAR⁷, the largest US-based repository for archaeology. Some other initial collaborations in ARIADNE have been maintained, most notably the collaboration with the providers of the PeriodO gazetteer (see [Section 4.3.4](#)).

Network extension and benefits for associate partners

In ARIADNEplus 17 organisations have joined the network as associate partners, strengthening it in some countries, such as Austria, Bulgaria, Greece, Portugal and the United Kingdom, and expanding its presence to Croatia, North Macedonia, Serbia, Slovak Republic and Turkey.

Through associate projects, the network also expands thematically, e.g., through the ROCEEH project of the Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities in the field of paleoanthropology in regions of Africa, the Levant, Eurasia and Europe; through DataARC of the North Atlantic Biocultural Organization (NABO) in the research field of long-term human ecodynamics.

Associate partners are not funded from the ARIADNEplus project budget, but have invested significant time and staff resource in their contributions, particularly those who prepared data for aggregation and integration in the ARIADNE portal. This also concerns data providers who have not joined as formal associate partners, for example, Historic Environment Scotland, Historic England, and the Portable Antiquities Scheme at the British Museum. These institutions have been enthusiastic about integrating their rich data in the ARIADNE portal, cross-searchable and accessible by researchers and other users.

Thus, associate partners and others have given freely of their time, and it is estimated that through their unpaid effort, ARIADNEplus has leveraged at least an additional 24 person months over the duration of the project (ARIADNEplus 2022c: 20).

Worth noting are also impacts regarding institutional policies and capacity building that associate partners perceived from participating in ARIADNEplus, particularly by partners in some countries, e.g., in central and south-eastern Europe, where there has been little previous tradition of open access to research data in archaeology and heritage.

Furthermore, European schools abroad, including the French and British schools based in Athens and Ankara, have been keen to participate. These schools often lack IT resources but sit on massive archaeological legacy archives. Therefore, they appreciated ARIADNEplus as an opportunity for digital capacity building, networking and sharing of their data.

That so many organisations have wanted to join ARIADNEplus as associate partner, and been willing to commit time and resources to it, clearly bodes well for the sustainability of the ARIADNE initiative beyond the existing funded project.

Overview of the ARIADNEplus associate partners

This overview briefly presents the 17 European organisations which have already joined the ARIADNEplus network as associate partner based on a cooperation agreement.

- **Monuments Board of the Slovak Republic:** The Monuments Board is the State administration authority in Slovakia established by law for the protection of monuments and historic sites, including archaeology. At present, the MBSR carries out the Monument Information System project, which aims to utilise geospatial technologies in the management of monuments and historic sites, and in the registers of archaeological sites and fieldworks, as well as making these datasets available to professionals and the general public. The MBSR is interested to learn from

⁷ tDAR - The Digital Archaeological Record, <https://www.tdar.org>

the ARIADNEplus portal and services development and training offer, and may provide data in the next phase of the ARIADNE initiative.

- **Directorate for Protection of Cultural Heritage (DPCH), Ministry of Culture of the Republic of North Macedonia:** As a governmental administrative body, the Directorate coordinates the implementation of national and strategically significant programmes and projects for the protection of cultural heritage. The DPCH is also in charge of maintaining the national register of cultural heritage and the largest database of digitised content related to archaeological monuments and sites. The DPCH is interested staying up to date through the ARIADNE initiative with the latest European research data policies and technological developments, and may provide data in the next phase of the ARIADNE initiative.
- **Mathematical Institute of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts (Serbia):** MISANU is a leading institution in Serbia regarding the digitisation and provision of access to scientific and cultural heritage. They will provide to the ARIADNE data portal a collection of data related to cultural monuments of exceptional importance in Serbia, i.e., monuments included in the UNESCO World Heritage List (contribution already prepared).
- **Institute of Archaeology in Zagreb (Croatia),** is the leading scientific organisation for applied archaeological research in Croatia, covering all archaeological periods and methods. The Institute also develops ARHINDOKS, the Archaeological Information Documentation Centre, with thematic databases of archaeological sites and finds. Furthermore, it publishes scientific and professional journals, monographs and proceedings, and also organises international events in Croatia. The Institute participates in ARIADNEplus working groups, investigates a potential contribution of data, and supports the testing of the data portal and other services.
- **British School at Athens (Greece),** promotes research in all disciplines pertaining to Greek lands, from fine art to archaeometry and in all periods to modern times. The School has a database of archaeological activities (e.g., excavations, surveys, study seasons, laboratory work) they conducted and facilitated from 1889 to the present day; database records will be included in the ARIADNE data portal (contribution already prepared).
- **British Institute at Ankara (Turkey),** supports research in Turkey and the Black Sea region in a wide range of fields including archaeology, ancient and modern history, heritage management, and others. The BIAA has a library, plant, bone, epigraphic and pottery collections and an archive of source materials produced in the course of archaeological research from the 1940s to the present day. The BIAA is building a regional digital repository (Çayırezmez 2020; Çayırezmez et al. 2021) and aims to provide collection records for their archives to the ARIADNE portal.
- **École française d'Athènes (Greece),** is a centre of advanced research and academic development in the humanities whose core mandate is the study of Greece in its Balkan and Mediterranean contexts, from prehistoric time to the present. The EFA research centre holds a unique archival collection of materials from its expeditions to sites of Greece and other Mediterranean countries (e.g., 657,000 photographs, 56,000 maps and drawings, and numerous handwritten documents). EFA will provide to the ARIADNE portal records from their Archimage database (contribution already prepared).
- **University of Minho, Archaeology Unit (Portugal):** The Archaeology Unit carries out research and develops databases in different themes of ARIADNEplus. A first contribution of data will focus on two datasets of Roman coins (the data supply is being prepared).
- **University of Innsbruck, Department of Archaeologies (Austria),** conducts research projects in the fields of Pre- and protohistory, Classical Archaeology and Archaeology of the Roman Provinces as well as the Middle Ages and Modern Period. Their lead researcher for ARIADNEplus contributed to

the development of a CIDOC CRM extension and an application profile for the project. A dataset of open research data created in the project “Prehistoric copper production in the eastern and central Alps” is already included in the ARIADNE data portal.

- ***Census of Antique Works of Art and Architecture Known in the Renaissance, Humboldt University of Berlin (international)***: Started in the 1940s as an art history project, the Census has become an international research database, hosted since the 1990s by the Institut für Kunst- und Bildgeschichte at the Humboldt Universität zu Berlin. Among the advisory board members are the Bibliotheca Hertziana (Max Planck Institute for Art History) in Rome, the Getty Research Institute (Los Angeles), and the Warburg Institute (London). The Census database documents the knowledge of antique monuments in the Renaissance era (1400-1600), relating over 20,000 antique monuments to over 60,000 Renaissance works that referenced them such as texts, drawings, paintings, prints, medals, etc. Beginning in 2009, the Census database also began to incorporate data from the Corpus Winckelmann on the knowledge of antiquities in the 17th and 18th centuries. Since 2022, efforts have been underway to apply the CIDOC CRM in view of linking the Census data with other resources, which the ARIADNE portal will enable, prospectively in 2023.
- ***CISA - Centro Interdipartimentale di Servizi di Archeologia (Università di Napoli L'Orientale)***: CISA was founded in 1995 to support all the archaeological activities of the University L'Orientale of Naples through the services provided by the staff of the structure and through the scientific equipment necessary for the implementation of documentation and digital cataloguing. Over the years CISA developed expertise in the field of archaeological data analysis and processing (GIS, standards, metadata, 3D surveys, photogrammetry, BIM, and so forth). CISA is interested in sharing and exchanging with the ARIADNE network, knowledge about archaeological data types, systems and tools.
- ***DataARC - Enabling Research on the Long-Term Human Ecodynamics of the North Atlantic, North Atlantic Biocultural Organization (NABO)***: DataARC was initiated by the NABO community, with funding by the US National Science Foundation, to develop a digital research infrastructure and tools supporting interdisciplinary research on long-term human-ecodynamics in the North Atlantic. To demonstrate dataARC's capabilities, the project has brought together fifteen datasets from paleoclimate and environment research, archaeological excavations and historical documents, with a geographic focus on Iceland, Greenland and the Orkneys. The collaboration with dataARC focuses on standards for data aggregation and researchers' requirements for virtual research environments.
- ***IsoArch - Isotope database bioarchaeological samples***: IsoArch based in Sarzeau, France, is an open-access and collaborative isotope database dedicated to bioarchaeological samples from all periods and all around the world (www.isoarch.eu). IsoArch aims to make the whole IsoArch dataset available to ARIADNEplus for integrating purposes.
- ***ROCEEH - The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans, Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities***: Initiated in 2008 by the Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities, the mission of the multidisciplinary research project ROCEEH is to generate a systemic understanding of “becoming human”, focusing on the development until 20,000 years before the present in Africa and Eurasia. Research centres of the long-term project are located at the Universities of Heidelberg and Tübingen and the Senckenberg Research Institute in Frankfurt am Main. The project has already provided 7517 data records from the ROCEEH Out-of-Africa Database (ROAD) to the ARIADNE data portal. The ROCEEH team has also shared lessons learned in the process of increasing the FAIRness of data in conference sessions organised by ARIADNEplus (Kandel et al. 2022a/b/c).

- **Thanados - The Anthropological and Archaeological Database of Sepultures, Natural History Museum in Vienna:** Thanados provides a database of investigated burials of Early Medieval cemeteries (600 until 1100 AD) from the area of present-day Austria. The Thanados database and research tools are based on the OpenAtlas system and use CIDOC CRM and domain-specific vocabularies. Thanados data records have already been included in the ARIADNE data portal.
- **Takin.solutions Ltd. (Bulgaria),** is a consultation and services company that supports the implementation of information management systems in the cultural heritage sector. The company has developed solutions based on semantic models and techniques for international clients, including the Canadian Heritage Information Network (CHIN), the Max Planck Institutes for the History of Science and for Art History (Bibliotheca Hertziana), and the Swiss Art Research Infrastructure (SARI). Takin.solutions is also an official service provider for the ARCHES Heritage Inventory and Management System. They participate in ARIADNEplus working groups, support training in the application of the CIDOC CRM ontology, and contribute to the development of tools for data analysis and synthesis.
- **University College London, Department of Information Studies (UK),** is an associate technical partner working with ARIADNEplus partner University of South Wales on advanced Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools for the extraction of terms from archaeological documents. These tools use controlled vocabularies and linguistic patterns to automatically suggest subject metadata for archaeological texts, such as grey literature reports.

Finally, regarding an extension of the ARIADNE initiative towards Africa, there is the **North African Heritage Archive Network (NAHAN)** project⁸. NAHAN was initiated during the original ARIADNE project and is being led by ARIADNEplus partner Associazione Internazionale di Archeologia Classica (Italy). This long-term project aims to catalogue and make accessible online North African excavation archives held by regional and European institutions. A data platform has been implemented by Archéologie et Philologie d'Orient et d'Occident (AOOrOc), a research centre of the CNRS, and work is ongoing to produce records based on standards promoted by ARIADNEplus (Fentress et al. 2022).

With the project **Endangered Archaeology in the Middle East and North Africa (EAMENA)**⁹ a possible integration of their data in ARIADNE based on a Linked Open Data approach has been discussed. EAMENA is led by the Oxford School of Archaeology and with funding by the Arcadia Fund¹⁰ developed a database of mapped and remotely sensed at-risk archaeological sites in the MENA region. According to recent discussion of Archaeology Data Service (ADS) with the Arcadia Fund, there is the possibility of archiving the data of EAMENA and other Arcadia funded projects¹¹ in the ADS repository, which would in future enable to include the data in the ARIADNE portal.

4.1.4 Understanding and supporting community needs

ARIADNEplus investigates user community needs to ensure that their demands are being met by the technical and other services, such as training. The core groups of the community are researchers in archaeology and cultural heritage, data managers of research projects, and managers of repositories of research institutes, heritage agencies and museums.

⁸ NAHAN - North African Heritage Archive Network, <https://www.nahanweb.org>

⁹ EAMENA - Endangered Archaeology in the Middle East and North Africa, <https://eamena.org>

¹⁰ Arcadia Fund, <https://www.arcadiahfund.org.uk>

¹¹ For example, Maritime Endangered Archaeology in the Middle East and North Africa (MarEA), Mapping Africa's Endangered Archaeological Sites and Monuments (MAEASaM), MASHA - Mapping Archaeological Heritage in South Asia (MASHA).

Other groups are being addressed where appropriate. For example, the project integrates metal-detectorists and other finds by amateurs in countries where this is permitted, and the registration of finds in national databases has been enabled.¹² Records of such databases managed by ARIADNEplus partners and others are being integrated in the ARIADNE data portal.

The sections that follow highlight some results of the broad survey on community needs (2019), the FAIR archaeological repositories survey (2021), the focus groups with archaeological professionals and heritage managers (2021/2022), and the study on the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on archaeology and cultural heritage (2021). Furthermore, the needs of ARIADNEplus thematic communities have been investigated in workshops on use cases of virtual research environments, which are described in [Section 4.5.3](#).

User community needs survey

In 2019, ARIADNEplus carried out a survey on user community needs regarding data sharing, access and (re)use, enhanced and new services, and training needs (ARIADNEplus 2019). The survey results are based on 484 questionnaires received from all 27 ARIADNEplus partner countries and a few other countries.

The organisational background of most respondents is a university or public research organisation (53%), museum (19%), governmental institution (15%) or a private company or research institute (8%). Regarding professional activities, 53% are archaeological researchers (field work), 9% laboratory-based researchers, 13% managers of an institutional repository or other data access services, 7% managers of project databases, 7% directors of an archaeological institute or research centre/laboratory, 12% other (various academic, technical and data management activities).

The most important survey results concern the enhanced and new services for researchers and data managers. A very encouraging survey result was that respondents very much appreciated services that were already implemented by the original ARIADNE project (and which they may have already used): register a dataset in a portal that allows the searching of data from many providers; discover and access archaeological data stored in repositories in different European and other countries; spatially and/or chronologically defined search options.

Services for searching and visualising geospatial datasets were the highest ranked among the new services, and the ARIADNE data portal has in the meantime been enhanced to support this (see [Section 4.4](#)). Respondents were also particularly interested in services for working with visual content (e.g., 3D models, LiDAR imagery). The original ARIADNE Visual Media Services have been developed further and are being provided on the Cloud-based D4Science platform. Furthermore, respondents were very interested in using Linked Data to interlink their own and other datasets. The ARIADNEplus Linked Open Data has been made accessible to external developers for interlinking datasets (see [Section 4.3.6](#)).

Regarding the training needs of eight suggested topics, both researchers and data managers appreciated most the training in the application of the FAIR data principles, which ARIADNEplus is committed to support. Among the other topics, respondents were also interested in training on managing datasets of a large archaeological project as well as depositing project datasets in a digital repository.

Actually, between 86.6–94.5% of the respondents regarded the different training options as very helpful or helpful. Therefore, the themes were adopted for structuring the training resources included

¹² For example, Digitale Metaldektektorfund (DIME) in Denmark, FindSampo in Finland, Portable Antiquities of the Netherlands (PAN), Portable Antiquities Scheme (PAS) in England and Wales.

in the ARIADNEplus Training Hub.¹³ Figures for the Training Hub access and the provision of in-person and online training are given in *Section 4.10*.

Survey of archaeological repositories

In 2021, ARIADNEplus carried out a survey of archaeological repositories for an evaluation of the extent to which their current data policies and practices conform to ideals of FAIR and open access data, which increasingly inform regulations of research funders, councils and other institutions. 60 archaeological repositories related to the SEADDA network and others (of which 43 operative and 17 currently being set up) participated in the survey which makes the reality check of this survey the largest thus far for repositories of a single discipline (Geser et al. 2022).

The survey responses provide information on one or more repositories located in most European countries, as well as repositories in other countries. Most of the organisations at which the repositories are located or will be based are research centres or institutes (20), universities (13), and heritage authorities or agencies (16). The sample of repositories also includes five housed at museums, two at archival institutions, and one is being provided by a national archaeological association.

The survey results can enable heritage and research authorities, councils and other institutions to reinforce or put in place regulations and support that bring current repository policies and practices closer to the envisaged ideals of FAIR and open access data.

Among the many results of the survey, the following are the most important:

- *Support of FAIR and open data policies:* A clear position from heritage authorities is most needed in this regard; 39 repositories (65%) required regulations and 36 (60%) clear guidelines from the authorities. Other support is also needed; for example, 28 repositories (47%) considered training of repository staff to support new policies on open/FAIR data as important.
- *Data discovery:* 24 repositories (40%) do not have a metadata search interface and 35 (58%) do not share metadata with external search platforms. More advice is needed on how metadata can be provided to national and thematic search platforms.
- *Control of data access:* At 21 repositories (35%), data are only accessible to legitimate registered users and/or by permission. In addition, 15 repositories (25%) have restrictions for some data, while 24 repositories (40%) have an open access approach (i.e., no registration is required). These results corroborate that open access regulations by heritage authorities, councils and other institutions are necessary for reducing barriers to data access.
- *Improving access with technology and data standards:* In this regard, repositories often considered to improve or replace the existing data management system (50%), improve the quality of metadata (57%), provide metadata to external search platforms/engines (45%), use Linked Data to interlink internal and other (meta)data (43%).

A critical issue is that many repositories do not collect and analyse information about data access and reuse:

- *Data access:* Of 56 respondents, 29 (52%) said that their repository does not collect and analyse data access figures, although this might allow identification of where access procedures could be improved and how better reporting of repository usage could be developed.
- *Data reuse:* No information about data reuse (e.g., references in publications and other sources) is being collected according to 47 of 56 respondents (84%), despite the fact that reuse for new

¹³ ARIADNEplus Training Hub, <https://training.ariadne-infrastructure.eu>

research and other purposes best demonstrates that funds for data preservation and access are well invested.

Nonetheless, it is encouraging for the open/FAIR data agenda that 24 of the 27 repositories that analyse data access reported that during the COVID-19 pandemic there was increased access, with increases ranging from 5% to over 100%. It seems likely that the COVID-19 crisis made archaeologists more aware of the importance of publicly shared data, data repositories and discovery and access services.

Focus groups with archaeological professionals and heritage managers

As a research data infrastructure, ARIADNEplus' core community is among research institutions, researchers and managers of research data repositories. Archaeological professionals and heritage managers of national and regional agencies, heritage sites and museums are generally less aware of research data infrastructures which may be relevant for their work.

Therefore, ARIADNEplus carried out a series of focus groups with professionals in cultural heritage and archaeology, i.e., archaeologists working in commercial, contract or preventive archaeology (ARIADNEplus 2022c: 18-19). Three focus groups meeting were organised by CARARE (December 2021, February 2022, March 2022) and involved professionals from Bulgaria, Croatia, Finland, Ireland, North Macedonia, Scotland, Serbia, Slovak Republic, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden. The fourth focus group was organised by ICCU and PIN (March 2022) and involved practitioners in Italy. Over 20 archaeological professionals and heritage managers participated in the focus groups.

Among the organisations participants are working for are the Directorate for Protection of Cultural Heritage in North Macedonia, the Finnish Heritage Agency, Historic Scotland, Monuments Board of the Slovak Republic, the Swedish National Heritage Board, Transport Infrastructure Ireland, Urban Planning Institute of the Republic of Slovenia, Cooperative Society adArte srl (Italy), Superintendence of Archaeology, Fine Arts and Landscape of Umbria Department. A few participants from academic institutions had a focus on the documentation of cultural heritage, e.g., the Laboratorio de Documentación Geométrica del Patrimonio, University of the Basque Country, Spain.

The focus groups raised awareness of ARIADNEplus, the Portal, Training Hub and other resources, brought insight into their related interests and needs, and resulted in a new associate partner from Serbia joining the network.

During each session, participants were asked to give feedback on the ARIADNE portal, on potential benefits to their organisation (or organisations in their country or region) in participating in the initiative, on which aspects of the Training Hub they found most useful, and were given opportunities to make comments and suggestions:

- Participants liked the ARIADNE portal and found the search facilities to be user-friendly but commented that its value for heritage management depends largely on the availability of data for their country or region. Several participants asked how easy it is to upload data to the system.
- One respondent commented that ARIADNEplus can be inspirational, noting that as more content is shared for their country, use by researchers and professionals will increase. However, one participant noted that contract archaeologists are more likely to use national systems (in the national language) and less likely to need data from across country boundaries.
- In general, participants were interested in the topics of the Training Hub such as open data and science practices, and perceived a need for training in the digital humanities. Participants commented that for their organisation (or organisations in their country or region) it would be useful to have access to training materials on key topics in their national language.

- Participants also thought that ARIADNEplus has the potential to inspire new systems developments, for example, regarding the structuring and standardisation of systems of heritage management institutions.

Professionals in cultural heritage and archaeology were also addressed through the “ARIADNEplus for Archaeological Sites and Built Structures” session at the annual Symposium of the Association ARA – Architecture.Restoration.Archaeology (Romania), 5-7 May 2022. The symposium brings together a wide range of professionals working on the protection of sites, monuments and historic building. The ARIADNEplus session focused on what the project can offer regarding standards on digital documentation, data services and training materials. The session was held online and attracted 41 participants (ARIADNEplus 2022b).

Study on the impact of COVID-19 on archaeology and cultural heritage

In 2021, ARIADNEplus carried out a study to understand the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the sectors of archaeology and cultural heritage, and how the project could contribute to recovery, beneficial changes in digital practices, and future resilience (Geser 2021).

Impact on archaeology

In academic archaeology, site-based fieldwork and public archaeology, as well as laboratory work has been affected. Planned fieldwork campaigns and field schools with students and volunteers in 2020 and 2021 had to be cancelled. In coming years, less funding for archaeological projects may be available.

The impact on preventive or development-led archaeology carried out by companies and public organisations appears to be lower, at least compared to the economic crisis of some years ago which forced many contract archaeology businesses to close. However, some companies had to furlough staff and terminate temporary contracts; the situation for smaller companies and self-employed archaeologists has become insecure.

In academic archaeology, the knock-on effect of the COVID-19 crisis will be felt for a long time, particularly by graduate students and early-career archaeologists due to the disruptions of field and laboratory work and reduced employment chances. Established archaeologists had more time to analyse data from past field seasons, prepare publications, and applications for new research and public archaeology projects. Also, an increase in access to available data in digital repositories has been observed.

In addition to looking for reusable new and legacy data, archaeologists also explored tools for improving digital documentation and online platforms for collaborative research, for example virtual support by subject experts of local groups of field archaeologists.

Impact on cultural heritage

The impact of the COVID-19 crisis on cultural heritage institutions such as museums, monuments and other heritage sites and routes has been tremendous. Due to a drastic decrease in tourism and local attendance they have seen their in-person engagement plummet and a lot of income has been lost. The situation for many institutions and their staff has become insecure and even more so for freelance professionals.

The main positive effect highlighted by all impact surveys is that the COVID-19 crisis has brought about an increased focus of cultural heritage institutions on digital communication, online content and experiences of cultural heritage.

What increased most was use of social media platforms, whereas offering online experiences which require more time, resources and skills to develop was less common. Where well-resourced

institutions had already invested in online exhibitions, virtual museum applications, 3D models of heritage objects these were of course re-activated and promoted.

Such cultural heritage experiences were often highlighted in media articles; however, the COVID-19 crisis showed that many institutions still need to extend their online offer with engaging visual content, such as 3D models and other advanced content.

Conclusions for ARIADNEplus

The COVID-19 crisis arguably increases the value and impact of the work of ARIADNEplus on FAIR and open access data (e.g., DMP tools, guidance and training), digital repositories and data discovery and access services.

Archaeologists who, due to the COVID-19 crisis, could not carry out fieldwork to collect new data showed interest in exploiting already existing documentation. For these purposes, the ARIADNEplus Cloud-based Natural Language Processing (NLP) services, which support extraction of information from archaeological documents such as fieldwork reports, are relevant (see [Section 4.5.2](#)).

During the COVID-19 crisis archaeologists also used online platforms to carry out research tasks, for example virtual support by subject experts of local groups of field archaeologists. ARIADNEplus provides virtual research environment (VRE) services for different tasks and data types (see [Section 4.5.3](#)).

The ARIADNEplus Visual Media Services (VMS) are relevant for cultural heritage institutions interested in using 3D models and other advanced visual content (e.g., Reflectance Transformation Imaging – RTI) for the presentation of heritage sites and objects. The VMS have already been presented to heritage institutions and supporting businesses to collect their interest and requirements for using the service (see [Section 4.8](#)).

ARIADNE surveys – an important resource for the sector

The ARIADNE surveys in 2013 and 2019 are the only existing large surveys on data practices of archaeologists in Europe. The 2013 survey includes over 600 filled questionnaires in the analysis, while the 2019 survey includes 484 questionnaires (ARIADNE 2014; ARIADNEplus 2019a).

Consequently, survey results are often referenced by researchers to explain developments in digital archaeology and to underpin arguments (e.g., Brandsen et al. 2021: 3; De Bruin 2019: 70; Faniel et al. 2020: 2; Huvila et al. 2021; Katsianis et al. 2022: 540[35]; Lombardo et al. 2020: 3; PARTHENOS 2016: 34; Štular 2021: Sec.3.2). For example, Huvila et al. (2021), introducing a session at the CAA 2021 conference, acknowledge their usefulness for understanding the *“practices of knowledge production in and about archaeology”*.

The survey of archaeological repositories in 2021, with participation of 60 repositories of research centres and heritage agencies, is the largest thus far on the compliance with FAIR and open access data principles of repositories of a single discipline. Therefore, in future some publications referencing it can be expected. In recent publications, for example, it is mentioned as underlining the challenges of managing the diverse data that is being produced in archaeology (Huggett 2022: Sec.4), and having investigated the guidance and support needed to make archaeological repositories and data FAIR (Spyrou et al. 2022: Sec.5).

4.1.5 Summary of results

Growing ARIADNE network of partners

The ARIADNEplus project started in January 2019 with a consortium of 41 partners, up from 23 of the original ARIADNE project, including also partners from the United States, Argentina, Israel and Japan.

Thus, the ARIADNE initiative is now present more strongly across Europe and in other world regions as well. The inclusion of data from the international partners in the ARIADNE data portal demonstrates that the initiative has the objective and the capacity to expand its data pool beyond Europe.

Most of the archaeological partners of ARIADNEplus also participate in the COST Action SEADDA (Saving European Archaeology from a Digital Dark Age), a partnership with representation from nearly all European countries, not only those in the EU.

SEADDA and ARIADNEplus have complementary goals. SEADDA is focussed on ensuring a more sustainable future for digital archaeological resources through the creation of new and better repositories, while ARIADNEplus supports finding and accessing data that is being shared through existing and new repositories.

ARIADNEplus increasingly receives requests from organisations wishing to join the ARIADNE network as associate partner based on a cooperation agreement: 17 European organisations have already joined the network, including heritage authorities, archaeological institutes, as well as domain research and technology centres.

These associates strengthen the presence of ARIADNE in some countries, Austria, Bulgaria, Greece, Portugal and the United Kingdom, and expand it to Croatia, North Macedonia, Serbia, Slovak Republic and Turkey.

Through associate projects the ARIADNE network also expands thematically, e.g., through the ROCEEH project in the field of paleoanthropology in regions of Africa, the Levant, Eurasia and Europe; through DataARC of the North Atlantic Biocultural Organization (NABO) in the research field of long-term human ecodynamics.

Benefits perceived by associate partners

Associate partners are not funded from the ARIADNEplus project budget, but have invested significant time and staff resource in their contributions, particularly those who prepared data for aggregation and integration in the ARIADNE portal; this has also been done by other providers who have not joined as associate partners. It is estimated that through their unpaid effort, ARIADNEplus has leveraged at least an additional 24 person months of work on data provision.

Associate partners perceived impacts regarding institutional policies and capacity building, particularly partners in countries where there has been little previous tradition of open access to research data in archaeology and heritage, i.e., countries in central and south-eastern Europe.

European schools abroad, including the French and British schools based in Athens and Ankara, have been keen to participate. These schools often lack IT resources but sit on massive archaeological legacy archives. Therefore, they appreciated ARIADNEplus as an opportunity for digital capacity building, networking and sharing of their data.

That many organisations have wanted to join ARIADNEplus as associate partner, and been willing to commit time and resources to it, clearly bodes well for the sustainability of the ARIADNE initiative beyond the existing funded project.

Recognition by major archaeological bodies

The value and impact of the ARIADNE initiative is confirmed by its growth and recognition by the main bodies for archaeology in Europe. The initiative is being recognised by the European Archaeological Council (EAC) and the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA) as the leading integrator of archaeological data resources in Europe and beyond. Former and current presidents of both

institutions sit on the ARIADNEplus Scientific Advisory Board, ensuring regular dialogue with both organisations.

ARIADNEplus supports vital interests of these institutions in increasing access to archaeological data through provision of data management guidance and tools, conference sessions with a focus on FAIR and open access data, promotion of digital repositories, and data discovery and access.

Understanding and serving community needs

The development of the ARIADNE research infrastructure, portal and other services is based on a solid understanding of the community needs captured in surveys, focus groups and studies (e.g., the study on the impact of COVID-19).

The ARIADNE research infrastructure clearly supports community needs for services enabling data sharing, discovery and access. The results of the community needs survey in 2019, with responses of 484 researchers and data managers from all partner countries and others included in the analysis, confirmed high appreciation of the ARIADNE data services. The community also welcomes guidance from ARIADNEplus in the application of the FAIR data principles in archaeology.

The ARIADNE/plus surveys in 2013 and 2019 are the only existing large surveys on data practices of archaeologists in Europe. Consequently, results are often referenced by researchers to explain developments in digital archaeology and to underpin arguments.

The survey of archaeological repositories in 2021, with participation of 60 repositories of research centres and heritage agencies, provides an evaluation of the extent to which their current data policies and practices conform to ideals of FAIR and open access data. The recommendations given on how to promote further progress in this regard can inform related measures by major bodies such as the European Archaeological Council (EAC), national heritage agencies as well as research institutions.

Focus group meetings have been held with archaeological professionals and heritage managers (e.g., contract archaeologists, heritage administrators, curators of sites and museums), who are not the core intended users of the ARIADNE research data infrastructure. The participants liked the ARIADNE portal, finding the search facilities to be user-friendly, and asked how easy it is to upload data to the system.

Participants commented that its value for heritage management depends largely on the availability of data for their country or region, and that contract archaeologists are more likely to use national systems (in the national language) and less likely to need data from across country boundaries. Participants also thought that ARIADNEplus has the potential to inspire new system developments, for example, regarding the structuring and standardisation of systems of heritage management institutions.

Results of the study on the impact of COVID-19 on archaeology and cultural heritage indicated more interest by archaeological researchers to exploit already existing fieldwork reports and data. The repository survey confirmed this, as 24 of the 27 repositories which analyse data access reported an increase ranging from 5% to over 100%. For researchers and repository managers who want to extract information from large numbers of fieldwork reports, ARIADNEplus offers Cloud-based Natural Language Processing (NLP) services.

During the COVID-19 crisis archaeologists also used online platforms to carry out research tasks, for example virtual support by subject experts of local groups of field archaeologists. ARIADNEplus provides virtual research environment (VRE) services for different tasks and data types.

The COVID-19 crisis showed that many cultural heritage institutions still need to extend their online offer with advanced visual content. Here, the ARIADNEplus Visual Media Service (VMS) for 3D models and Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI) allows to explore heritage sites and objects in engaging

ways. The VMS has been presented to heritage institutions and supporting businesses to collect their interest and requirements for using the service.

4.2 Supporting the FAIR data agenda in archaeology

4.2.1 Expectation and project approach

RI Programme expectation

The list of statements on expected impacts in the RI Programme does not include a statement on FAIR data, although the European Commission has been one of the first adopters of the FAIR principles.¹⁴ However, the section “Specific features for Research Infrastructures” of the RI Programme, Part D, (i) Networking Activities, suggests that activities could focus on “*definition of data management plans to organise the efficient curation, preservation and provision of access to data collected or produced under the project, in line with the FAIR principles*”.

Meanwhile, the implementation of the FAIR principles has become a cornerstone of the research data policy of the European Commission and national research funders (Expert Group on FAIR Data 2018). Available FAIR data are also a core requirement for the success of the European Open Science Cloud initiative (EOSC FAIR Working Group 2020).

Project approach

ARIADNEplus is funded under the Horizon 2020 Programme as the Integrating Activity for archaeological research datasets. ARIADNEplus therefore is committed to advancing the FAIR data agenda in the archaeological sector in Europe (and beyond), in line with the respective policies of the European Commission and EU member states on open access to research data.

The advancement of the FAIR data agenda takes various forms, including: support of major European archaeological institutions in the promotion of FAIR, provision of guidance documents, and a FAIR data management plan (DMP) tool and templates for archaeologists (addressed in this section); training events and resources ([Section 4.10](#)), publications ([Section 4.11.2](#)) and sessions and presentations with a focus on FAIR data at conferences ([Section 4.11.3](#)).

4.2.2 Collaboration with major European archaeological institutions

The key role that the ARIADNE initiative plays as aggregator of archaeological data and driving the FAIR and open data agenda in archaeology is being recognised by the European Archaeological Council (EAC) and the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA). Former and current presidents of both archaeological institutions sit on the ARIADNEplus Scientific Advisory Board, ensuring regular dialogue with both organisations.

The European Archaeological Council (EAC) supports the management of archaeological heritage throughout Europe and provides a forum for national bodies enabling close cooperation and exchange of information. In February 2020, the EAC Board decided to collaborate with SEADDA, the “sister project” of ARIADNEplus, on progressing the FAIR data agenda in the archaeological sector.

The EAC Board has chosen SEADDA for this purpose as its network comprises partners engaged in archaeological data management from almost all European countries, including all ARIADNEplus

¹⁴ The FAIR data principles were published in March 2016 (Wilkinson et al. 2016) and quickly adopted by the European Commission, for example, in the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020 (26 July 2016) for Open Data Pilot projects (European Commission 2016).

archaeological partners. The EAC has taken a keen interest in the SEADDA review of the situation of archaeological data management in the European countries and also in the United States, Argentina, Israel and Japan.

The EAC co-sponsored the open access publication of the national review reports in the journal *Internet Archaeology* (Jakobsson et al. 2021). This review was followed by the survey on the “FAIRness” of archaeological repositories conducted by ARIADNEplus in collaboration with SEADDA and also published in *Internet Archaeology* (Geser et al. 2022; see [Section 4.1.4](#)).

In March 2020, Felipe Criado-Boado, then president of the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA), informed the managing directors of ARIADNEplus that the EAA Board endorses the FAIR principles and proposed a collaboration with ARIADNEplus for the promotion of the principles in archaeology.

The COVID-19 crisis 2020-2021 has affected these collaborations, as both high-level bodies were more concerned with supporting sector organisations in other respects. However, ARIADNEplus continued to support the vital interests of these institutions by providing practical FAIR data management guidance and tools for archaeologists (see below), training events and resources (see [Section 4.10](#)), publications (see [Section 4.11.2](#)), and sessions and presentations with a focus on FAIR data at EAA and other international conferences, e.g., Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology (CAA), Cultural Heritage and New Technologies (CHNT) and several others (see [Section 4.11.3](#)).

4.2.3 FAIR data guidance

Ever more research funders now require researchers to create and share FAIR data. Therefore, researchers in archaeology and related domains need guidance on what is meant by FAIR data and how to create and make it available. For this purpose, the ARIADNE initiative adopted the FAIRify guide developed by the humanities and social sciences RI cluster project PARTHENOS (H2020, 2015-2019), in which members of ARIADNEplus had leading roles also regarding these guidelines.

The FAIRify guide offers twenty guidelines to align the efforts of research data producers and archivists making the data as reusable as possible based upon the FAIR Principles. Each guideline has recommendations for both, as it is recognised that different priorities may apply to each case.

ARIADNEplus and SEADDA support the dissemination of the FAIRify guide, which is already available in several languages. A webpage on the ARIADNEplus website presents the list of the available language versions¹⁵, while the documents are stored in the open access Zenodo repository. Zenodo provides figures for the unique downloads of each language version.

Table 1: FAIRify guidelines: unique downloads per 14.06.2021 and 20.12.2022:

Language versions	Unique downloads 14.06.2021	Unique downloads 20.12.2022
English	1,108	1,596
Portuguese	271	338
Turkish	257	384
German	219	336
Czech	198	287
Italian	132	175
French	115	182

¹⁵ ARIADNEplus: Guidelines to FAIRify data management and make data reusable, <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/resources/other-reports/>

Greek	106	292
Hungarian	56	91
	2,462	3,681

At present, the unique downloads of the FAIRify guidelines in the different languages amount to 3,681, while in June 2021 the unique downloads stood at 2,462 (ARIADNEplus 2021a: 35), an increase of 49.5%. Not surprisingly, the English version has been downloaded most (1,596), but also the downloads of other language versions are significant, e.g., the Turkish (384) and Portuguese (338) versions.

The FAIRify guide is relevant for both researchers and repositories, indeed, many repositories struggle as much as the researchers with understanding and applying the FAIR data principles (Dunning et al. 2017; Ivanović et al. 2019).¹⁶ A common element is data management plans (DMPs), as ever more research funders now require researchers to create one with the goal to share FAIR data through an accessible digital repository.

4.2.4 Data management plan tool and templates

ARIADNEplus promotes the standardisation of data management plans (DMPs) and practices of archaeological researchers and research groups. Many generic templates for a DMP are available from research support centres. However, there is a growing understanding that different domains of research have common but also different requirements, which should be taken into account. In Europe, domain-specific DMP protocols are being promoted by Science Europe (Science Europe 2018 and 2021).¹⁷

ARIADNEplus offers an online Data Management Plan Tool¹⁸ which supports archaeological data managers and archaeologists who want (or are obliged) to make a DMP for producing and sharing data that comply with the FAIR data principles.

A complication is that the requirements for a DMP, although similar in intention, vary across research funders and organisations. Therefore, ARIADNEplus currently provides the tool with three DMP templates:

- the Protocol for Archaeological Data Management, which is based on the widely recognised Science Europe guidance for research data management and the principle of “comply or explain”;
- the ARIADNEplus DMP Researcher Template for Archaeological Datasets, developed from the Horizon 2020 requirements and tailored to community standards and practices;
- the Horizon Europe Template for Archaeological Datasets which includes links to information and suggestions for answering the questions of the template; the related guide can also be consulted for the above protocol and template¹⁹.

By using the tool, archaeological researchers can better understand the requirements for FAIR data and save a lot of time in drawing up a fit for purpose DMP. An online workshop on the DMP tool and

¹⁶ These surveys are on various repositories whereas the ARIADNEplus survey focused on archaeological repositories specifically (see [Section 4.1.4](#)).

¹⁷ Science Europe is an association of major public research funders and research organisations in Europe, <https://www.scienceurope.org>

¹⁸ ARIADNEplus Data Management Plan Tools (P. Doorn, DANS & P. Ronzino, PIN, Version 1.0, 25 March 2022, CC-BY), <https://vast-lab.org/dmp/index.html>

¹⁹ ARIADNEplus Guide for Archaeological Data Management Planning (P. Doorn, DANS & P. Ronzino, PIN, Version 1.0, 25 March 2022, CC-BY), <https://training.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/dmp-guidance/>

templates in March 2022 was attended by 89 participants (Geser 2022). Users of the DMP tool have so far prepared 92 DMPs.²⁰

It is worth noting that between 2020-2021, the ARIADNEplus DMP team collaborated with OpenAIRE on the development of their Argos²¹ DMP tool. The collaboration improved both the ARIADNEplus DMP templates and the Argos tool regarding the user navigation and information on research data management (Papadopoulou 2020 and 2021: 21-22).

4.2.5 Summary of results

Promoting the FAIR data agenda in archaeology

ARIADNEplus is committed to promoting the FAIR data agenda in the archaeological sector in Europe (and beyond), in line with the respective policies of the European Commission and EU member states on open access to publicly funded research data.

The Board of the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA) endorsed the FAIR principles and proposed a collaboration with ARIADNEplus for their implementation in archaeology. The European Archaeological Council (EAC) works with SEADDA, the “sister project” of ARIADNEplus, on progressing the FAIR data agenda in the sector.

The promotion of FAIR data by ARIADNEplus takes different forms, including recommendations and dissemination of guidance, a FAIR data management plan (DMP) tool and templates for archaeologists, FAIR as part of training activities and materials, and sessions and presentations at domain conferences.

FAIR guidance and DMP tool

Researchers and data managers in archaeology look for practical guidance on what is meant by FAIR data and how to create and make it available. For broad dissemination in the sector, ARIADNEplus adopted the PARTHENOS FAIRify guide, which is relevant for both researchers and repositories and available in nine language versions. At present, the unique downloads of the FAIRify guide from the Zenodo repository amount to 3,681, while in June 2021 the unique downloads stood at 2,462, an increase of 49.5%.

ARIADNEplus promotes the standardisation of Data Management Plans (DMPs) and appropriate practices of archaeological researchers and projects, taking account of the requirements and standards for archaeological datasets. The ARIADNEplus DMP tool and templates have been developed specifically for archaeologists and conform to European Commission and Science Europe guidelines.

By using the tool, researchers can understand better the requirements for FAIR data and save a lot of time in drawing up a fit for purpose DMP. An online workshop on the DMP tool and templates in March 2022 was attended by 89 participants. Users of the DMP tool have so far prepared 92 DMPs.

4.3 Standardisation of archaeological datasets

4.3.1 Expectation and project approach

RI Programme expectation

The list of statements on expected impacts in the RI Programme does not include a statement that explicitly addresses standardisation, but the need for standardisation is implied in statement [8], “The

²⁰ Protocol for archaeological data template: 27; ARIADNEplus DMP template: 41; Horizon Europe template: 24.

²¹ ARGOS, <https://argos.openaire.eu>

integration of major scientific equipment or sets of instruments and of knowledge-based resources (collections, archives, structured scientific information, data infrastructures, etc.) leads to a better management of the continuous flow of data collected or produced by these facilities and resources.”

Integration of knowledge-based resources is hardly possible without standardisation, because standardisation makes data resources knowledge-based, i.e., based on established ontologies and terminology of the domain of knowledge. An explicit statement on standardisation can be found in the section “Specific features for Research Infrastructures” of the RI Programme, Part D, (i) Networking Activities, which considers “*definition of common standards, protocols and interoperability*” as a useful activity.

ARIADNEplus approach

The ARIADNE initiative aims for high quality integration of datasets from a wide range of archaeological domains of research in the data portal. The integration requires standardisation of the datasets for which the ISO standard CIDOC CRM (Conceptual Reference Model), domain-specific CRM extensions and application profiles, and domain vocabularies are being used.

Data providers map the schemas of their databases to the CRM-based ontology of the ARIADNE Data Catalogue (AO-Cat) and more specific CRM application profiles, e.g., based on the CRM extension for archaeological excavations (CRM_{archeo}). For the metadata of the data records, also general and domain-specific vocabularies are being used, for example, WGS84 for locations, the PeriodO gazetteer for cultural periods, and the Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus for subjects. The data records can then be aggregated and integrated in the ARIADNE portal.

The standardisation based on the CIDOC CRM, CRM extensions and common vocabularies promoted by ARIADNE/plus is increasingly being adopted by databases of archaeological research communities and projects. This increases the overall “FAIRness” of archaeological data, since the FAIR principles include as requirements that (meta)data should meet domain-relevant community standards, be described with accurate and relevant attributes, and encoded using a formal, shared and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation, i.e., the W3C Resource Description Framework (RDF) in the case of CIDOC CRM, Getty AAT and aligned vocabularies of ARIADNE data providers. The FAIR principles also include that the (meta)data should be registered in a searchable resource, i.e., the ARIADNE data portal.

4.3.2 Enhanced ARIADNE catalogue model

The original ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM) was developed using a set of classes and properties of the CIDOC CRM to map the metadata schemas of data resources to the model, which allowed to aggregate and integrate the metadata in the data catalogue. In the ARIADNE project, the data resources were mainly monument and site inventories, artefact databases, fieldwork reports and archives. ARIADNEplus mobilised a wider range of data types from different archaeological domains of research and integrates them at item level where possible.²²

The ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM) initiated the CRM-based standardisation of data catalogues in archaeology, cultural heritage and related fields of the humanities. In the PARTHENOS project²³, led by ARIADNE coordinator PIN and involving other partners, a more sophisticated data catalogue model has been developed. The PARTHENOS CRM_{pe} model²⁴, created for social sciences,

²² On the difference between collection- and item-level access see [Section 4.4.4](#).

²³ PARTHENOS (H2020, 5/2015-10/2019), <http://www.parthenos-project.eu>, has been a cluster project of humanities and social sciences research infrastructures.

²⁴ CRM_{pe} stands for CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM) – Parthenos entities (pe).

humanities and heritage catalogues, covers actors, activities, procedures, datasets and software (Frosini et al. 2018).

The CRMpe model has been taken up by ARIADNEplus to create the new ARIADNE Object Catalogue (AO-Cat) model (ARIADNEplus 2020),²⁵ which allows greater flexibility and detail for representing data collections as well as single data items. Still this model is intended for a common level of semantic description and linking of data resources. In addition, domain-specific CRM extensions and application profiles are needed when the goal is a deeper integration of item-level data to support research questions that require richer data modelling than the AO-Cat.

4.3.3 CIDOC CRM based standardisation of datasets

ARIADNEplus promotes standardisation of archaeological datasets based on the ISO standard CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (currently CRM v7.2, Bekiari et al. 2021). Without the CIDOC CRM as a common ontology there would be little chance of realising interoperability of data resources within the multi-disciplinary field of archaeology and cultural heritage, as achieved with the CRM-based ARIADNE data catalogue and portal.

Furthermore, the ARIADNE initiative is developing domain-specific CRM extensions. While always building on the core CRM ontology, such additions of new classes and properties allow a richer representation of conceptual relations of particular domains of archaeological research.

In the original ARIADNE project, the CRM extensions CRMarcheo for excavations (Doerr et al. 2019), CRMba for archaeological buildings (Ronzino et al. 2016; Ronzino 2019), and CRMtex for the study of ancient texts such as epigraphy have been developed, and in the case of CRMtex continued in ARIADNEplus (Felicetti & Murano 2020).

Promoted further by ARIADNEplus, the extensions are increasingly being adopted by archaeological database development and research projects, especially the CRMarchaeo (e.g., Aspöck et al. 2016; De Haas & Van Leusen 2020; Gergatsoulis et al. 2021b; Tufféry & Le Goff 2017). Also, the CRMba is increasingly recognised and inspires the modelling of historic building (e.g., Colucci et al. 2021; Gergatsoulis et al. 2021b; Parisi et al. 2019; Van Ruymbeke et al. 2018). Hence there is already a significant impact of the CRM-based standardisation of archaeological data management and research promoted by the ARIADNE initiative.

Examples from ARIADNE partners in France using CRMarchaeo illustrate that the usage can range from a whole digital research ecosystem like OpenArchaeo of the MASA Consortium²⁶ (Marlet et al. 2019a; Marlet & Rodier 2019), to large databases such as ArSol soil archives (Marlet et al. 2016), to single excavation archives (Marlet et al. 2019b).

Another example, not by an ARIADNEplus partner, is the Archaeological Interactive Report (AIR) system of the Laboratory for Digital Archaeology of the Department of Archaeology and Ancient History (DARK-Lab), Lund University (Sweden). The AIR system merges the open-source 3D visualisation platform 3DHOP (provided by the VCLab of ARIADNEplus partner CNR-ISTI) with the content management system Omeka S, using for the data description CRMarchaeo and other standards (Derudas & Nurra 2022). This approach has been applied to the online publication of excavations of the Iron Age site in Västra Vång, Sweden.²⁷

²⁵ Current version: ARIADNEplus AO-Cat Ontology, Version 1.1, 30/05/2022, <https://bit.ly/3iln0FJ>

²⁶ Mémoires des Archéologues et des Sites Archéologiques (MASA) is the archaeological consortium of the large Huma-Num digital research infrastructure, <https://masa.hypotheses.org>

²⁷ Västra Vång AIR, <https://omeka.ht.lu.se/s/vastra-vang/>; see the conceptual Graph at <https://omeka.ht.lu.se/s/vastra-vang/page/graph>

But the standardisation extends to other world regions as well. A particularly interesting example in international cooperation is the BE-ARCHAEO project²⁸, one of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie RISE Actions which bridge R&I domains in Europe and worldwide. In the BE-ARCHAEO project, the CRMarcheo is being used for data from excavations of Kofun period sites in Japan (Lombardo et al. 2020 and 2022).

Importantly, the ARIADNE initiative not only provides CRM extensions but also FORTH-ICS's 3M - Mapping Memory Manager system²⁹, the most advanced tool for mapping databases to the CRM and extensions or application profiles. The system can be accessed and used in the ARIADNEplus D4Science space.

4.3.4 Using and supporting core vocabularies

A major part of the data standardisation of the ARIADNE initiative in the field of archaeology is using and supporting essential domain vocabularies for data integration, such as the PeriodO gazetteer for cultural periods and the Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) for subjects of research objects. For locations, the general WGS84 (World Geodetic System 1984) standard is being used.

Sharing cultural periods through PeriodO

PeriodO³⁰ is a gazetteer that records the spatial and temporal boundaries assigned to a given cultural period by an authoritative source. The description of a period includes a unique identifier (URI) which allows clear and stable linking and finding of data resources which refer to the same period (Rabinowitz 2014; Rabinowitz et al. 2016; Shaw et al. 2018). ARIADNE adopted PeriodO because when users of the data portal conduct searches using named periods, e.g., "Iron Age", they can discover resources from different countries, although the "Iron Age" has a different time-span in France, England and Ireland.

In 2015, ARIADNE partners contributed one of the largest collections to the PeriodO system to date, containing 663 named periods (including time-ranges) for the territory of 24 European countries.³¹ For the PeriodO project, started in 2014, this was the "first major step" of growing the PeriodO dataset and user community (Rabinowitz et al. 2016: 53-54).

In ARIADNEplus, the contribution has been extended by partners and associates to 1,880 (ARIADNEplus 2022j), including sets of periods that are more detailed and sets for new partners in Europe as well as Japan, Argentina and a part of the USA. Among the associate projects, for example, ROCEEH contributed 145 periods from their Out of Africa Database which are being used in paleoanthropology and relate to regions of Africa, the Levant, Eurasia and Europe.

Through the PeriodO system, other institutions and projects can also use the cultural periods mobilised by ARIADNE/plus, enabling wider interlinking of data in Linked Data initiatives.

Using the Getty AAT as "semantic hub"

The Getty Research Institute provides vocabularies as Linked Open Data in RDF/SKOS format (Harpring 2018). These include the widely used, very rich and multilingual Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT)³²,

²⁸ BE-ARCHAEO (MSCA-RISE project, 2/2019-7/2023), <https://www.bearchaeo.com>

²⁹ Mapping Memory Manager - 3M (Institute of Computer Science, Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas), <http://www.ics.forth.gr/isl/3M>; source code, <https://github.com/isl/Mapping-Memory-Manager>

³⁰ PeriodO - Periods, Organized (Adam Rabinowitz et al., Institute of Classical Archaeology, University of Texas at Austin, USA), <http://perio.do>

³¹ PeriodO: ARIADNE Consortium (2015): ARIADNE Data Collection, <http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0qhb66> (note: ARIADNEplus contributions are not in this collection).

³² Getty Research Institute: The Getty Vocabularies, <http://vocab.getty.edu>

which ARIADNE has selected as a common “semantic hub” for the subjects of data collections and records.

In order to enable subject-based searches across collections and records, partners map subject terms from their thesauri or term lists to AAT concepts (Binding & Tudhope 2016). In ARIADNEplus, the total number of mappings of national and institutional vocabularies (in different languages) to the AAT amounts to nearly 21,500 of at present 30 partners, up from over 6,400 of 12 partners in the original ARIADNE project (ARIADNEplus 2022j).

Building on these mappings, the ARIADNE portal supports multi-lingual and granular cross-searching of the data resources. In an AAT terms-based search, the results for available narrower terms are also included. Consequently, if a broad term such as “weapons” is being used, records relating to more specific sub-categories such as swords, knives, clubs and the like are included in the search results, even where the respective terms are in other languages.

For the mapping of subject terms from “local” thesauri or term lists to the AAT, ARIADNEplus provides the browser-based interactive Vocabulary Matching Tool on the D4Science platform. Other data interoperability initiatives where providers use different vocabularies can benefit from using this freely available service or the stand-alone version.³³

4.3.5 Creation of domain-specific application profiles

The ARIADNE initiative aims to enable researchers from the multidisciplinary fields of archaeology to explore the growing pool of mobilised different data resources for their research questions. This is already possible to a certain degree with the search, filter and visualisation functionalities of the data portal. For deeper integration of item-level data and more specific searches, domain-specific CRM application profiles have been developed with a richer data modelling than the AO-Cat ontology of the ARIADNE data catalogue. Such application profiles use classes and properties from the overall CRM ontology, available extensions such as CRMarcheo for excavations, and required additions.

Development of application profiles

ARIADNEplus working groups for different research fields and data types have developed a first set of domain-specific application profiles or in the exercise found that the AO-Cat and other profiles or another approach provides enough capability for their data (ARIADNEplus 2022f: 12-23).

Application profiles have been developed for the following types of data:

- Heritage science data (CRMhs AP): for the encoding of information produced in the domains of inorganic materials studies and dating;
- Ancient DNA data (aDNA AP): to describe the aDNA wetlab methodologies integrated with the contextual information regarding the samples;
- Inscriptions, marks and graffiti data (AP): based on CRMtex which proved to fit well such data;
- Mortuary archaeology data (Mortuary AP): designed to model different types of burial data (Aspöck et al. 2022a; Aspöck et al. 2022b).

In addition, a draft Remote Sensing AP has been developed in the ipaast-czo project (UK) with contributions by ARIADNEplus researchers (Opitz et al. 2022). This CRM-based AP is intended to improve the

³³ Vocabulary Matching Tool (Hypermedia Research Group, University of South-Wales), <http://heritagedata.org/vocabularyMatchingTool/>; source code for download and installation available on GitHub, <https://github.com/cbinding/VocabularyMatchingTool>

interoperability of remote and near-surface sensing data between archaeological and precision agricultural applications.

It is also worth noting that the ARIADNEplus excavation modelling working group explored different options and challenges of modelling excavation data which are summarised in an available report (Katsianis & Nenova 2022); results of the working group have been presented at conferences and a public online workshop in June 2022 with nine presentations and many participants.³⁴ The final conclusion was that for basic modelling of excavation data the CRMarchaeo with some additions could be applied, while the results of the working group provide a basis for advanced modelling.

Testing and evaluation

Tests of application profiles have been conducted with representative ARIADNE datasets and relevant mappings for item-level data integration (ARIADNEplus 2022d: 22-30). The selected research fields were mortuary archaeology, epigraphy and numismatics. In the latter case, an alternative approach was tested using the AO-Cat and Nomisma ontologies for data integration. The testing was carried out with an experimental interface built on ResearchSpace³⁵, a free and open-source system developed at the British Museum with a focus on projects using the CIDOC CRM. The tests generally proved the feasibility of item-level integration for advanced searches in the three application domains. It also became clear that to exploit the results, domain researchers would need specialised interfaces and tools designed to support addressing their research questions.

Other approaches

In the work on the application profiles, it was also found that not all thematic sub-groups needed to develop their own profile, e.g., field surveys, metal detector surveys (artefacts), paleoanthropology, maritime and underwater archaeology. In such cases, using the AO-Cat model and other application profiles (e.g., heritage science data – CRMhs AP) proved to be sufficient for the encoding of core aspects of their datasets. Another approach, applied in the case of environmental archaeology, was to combine entities from the CIDOC CRM ecosystem with domain-specific vocabularies.

4.3.6 Applying Linked Open Data

Based on the new AO-Cat model or more specific CRM application profiles, the data records from different providers can be aggregated and integrated in the ARIADNE data portal. In the process, the records are transformed to Linked Data, which support searching and visualising results within the data portal.

The Linked Open Data (LOD) knowledge graph of over 175 million RDF triples also allows to use the semantic search and retrieval functionality, i.e., SPARQL queries (W3C 2013) to explore the data resources based on semantically defined relations between them. The semantic relations are defined by the CRM-based AO-Cat ontology and vocabularies used for the data records (e.g., Getty AAT). The ARIADNEplus LOD in the semantic graph database (GraphDB) can be accessed through the ARIADNEplus_Lab, which provides a set of tools for exploring and analysing the data (see *Section 4.5.3*).

Experts agree that LOD complies with most of the FAIR data principles³⁶, and the project took care to build the LOD knowledge graph following these principles. In recent years there have been more

³⁴ Semantic mapping of excavation data workshop (presentations), <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/semantic-mapping-of-excavation-data/>; 104 people registered for the event, simultaneous participation peaked at 62.

³⁵ ResearchSpace, <https://researchspace.org>

³⁶ For example, see Cox & Yu (2018), Hasnain & Rebholz-Schuhmann (2018), GO-FAIR: FAIRification Process, <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/fairification-process/>

adopters of the LOD approach in archaeology and related disciplines, but its application is still far from mainstream.

However, LOD-based ontologies and vocabularies that are already in the LOD Cloud³⁷ form hubs for linking data across providers, and ARIADNEplus uses such vocabularies, e.g., Getty AAT³⁸ and PeriodO³⁹. The ARIADNEplus LOD can also link to data from other providers, and vice versa, therefore, ARIADNEplus makes its LOD accessible so researchers and developers can use and interlink it with other data.

An ARIADNEplus LOD hackathon has been organised 29/30 November 2022 at the biannual Linked Past conference hosted by UoY-ADS in York (UK). The conference brings together the community interested in LOD applied to the study of the ancient and historical world, for example the Pelagios Network. The hackathon featured the ARIADNE data portal and LOD and challenged 15 participants to explore them for addressing research questions.

4.3.7 Summary of results

Standardisation based on CIDOC CRM

ARIADNEplus promotes standardisation and integration of archaeological datasets based on the ISO standard CIDOC CRM (Conceptual Reference Model) and domain-specific CRM extensions. Such extensions have been developed by ARIADNE experts, e.g., CRMarcheo (excavations), CRMba (heritage buildings) and CRMtex (e.g., inscriptions, marks, graffiti). These CRM extensions are increasingly being adopted for archaeological research projects and databases, particularly CRMarcheo and CRMba.

Importantly, the ARIADNE initiative not only provides CRM extensions but also FORTH-ICS's 3M (Mapping Memory Manager) system, the most advanced tool for mapping datasets to the CRM and extensions or application profiles. The system can be accessed and used in the ARIADNEplus D4Science space.

Data catalogue and deeper data integration

The data catalogue developed in the original ARIADNE project (ACDM) initiated the CRM-based standardisation of data catalogues in archaeology, cultural heritage and related fields of the humanities. Based on the jointly developed expertise, the new ARIADNE data catalogue model (AO-Cat) provides greater flexibility and detail to describe data collections as well as individual items.

Deeper integration of domain-specific datasets has been progressed by ARIADNEplus through the creation and testing of CRM-based application profiles, e.g., for ancient texts such as epigraphy and mortuary archaeology. The published application profiles can also inspire other projects which want to use CRM-based profiles for the integration of domain datasets.

Applying core domain vocabularies

A major part of the standardisation work of the ARIADNE initiative in the field of archaeology is demonstrating the power of using common vocabularies for data integration. The core examples here are the Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) and the PeriodO gazetteer for cultural period definitions.

For the subjects of their data resources, partners make semantic mappings of terms of "local" vocabularies (thesauri, term lists) to concepts of the large and multilingual Getty AAT. This enables subjects-based searches on the ARIADNE data portal across the integrated data collections and records. In

³⁷ Linked Open Data Cloud, <https://lod-cloud.net>

³⁸ <https://lod-cloud.net/dataset/getty-aat>

³⁹ <https://lod-cloud.net/dataset/periodo>

ARIADNEplus the total number of mappings (in different languages) to the AAT amounts to nearly 21,500 of at present 30 partners, up from over 6,400 of 12 partners in the original ARIADNE project.

For the mapping ARIADNEplus provides the browser-based interactive Vocabulary Matching Tool on the D4Science platform. Other data interoperability initiatives where providers use different vocabularies can benefit from using this freely available service.

The PeriodO gazetteer system provides unique identifiers (URIs) for cultural periods (including time-ranges), which allow stable linking of archaeological, ancient world and historical data resources that refer to the same period. Started in the original ARIADNE project with the largest contribution of 663 periods for 24 European countries, the collection has been extended by ARIADNEplus partners and associates to 1,880 periods, and more European and other countries, e.g., Argentina and Japan.

Through the PeriodO system, other institutions and projects can also use the periods mobilised by ARIADNE/plus, enabling wider interlinking of data which relate to the same periods.

Using and sharing Linked Open Data

Data records aggregated in the ARIADNE data portal are transformed to Linked Data which support searching and visualising results within the portal. The Linked Open Data (LOD) knowledge graph of over 175 million RDF triples can also be explored programmatically using SPARQL queries.

The semantic graph database (GraphDB) can be accessed by researchers and developers through the ARIADNEplus_Lab, which provides a user guide and a set of tools for exploring and analysing the LOD and possibly interlink it with other data.

Increasing the “FAIRness” of archaeological data

The data standardisation promoted by ARIADNEplus increases the overall “FAIRness” of archaeological data. The FAIR principles include as requirements that (meta)data should meet domain relevant community standards (i.e., CIDOC CRM), be described with accurate and relevant attributes (i.e., Getty AAT terms), and encoded using a formal, shared and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation (i.e., W3C RDF for Linked Data). The FAIR principles also include that the (meta)data should be registered in a searchable resource, i.e., the ARIADNE data portal.

4.4 Access to integrated knowledge-based resources

The previous section explained that standardisation makes data resources knowledge-based, i.e., based on established ontologies and terminology of the domain of knowledge (e.g., archaeology, cultural heritage). This section continues from the described standardisation, first addressing enhancements of the ARIADNE data portal, followed by the current status of dataset ingest, portal access and usage.

4.4.1 Expectation and project approach

RI Programme expectation

[8] *“The integration of major scientific equipment or sets of instruments and of knowledge-based resources (collections, archives, structured scientific information, data infrastructures, etc.) leads to a better management of the continuous flow of data collected or produced by these facilities and resources.”*

Integration and access to knowledge-based resources such as digital archives and collections is a core focus of EU funded Integrating Activities of research domains with an e-Infrastructure component. The e-Infrastructure is put in place to allow aggregation, discovery and access to data from distributed

domain archives and databases, i.e., the flow from data generators to data users, though not necessarily directly from scientific instruments.

In most cases of e-Infrastructure, there is no direct flow of data from scientific instruments to users, not even access to the massive raw data generated with the instruments. Rather, the data is prepared for access and (re)use from digital repositories and databases. Also, the ARIADNE e-Infrastructure has not been built specifically to access data-generating scientific instruments but to digital repositories providing access to different data resources, including scientific data.

Project approach

The ARIADNEplus European-level research infrastructure integrates international/national and thematically oriented data resources (databases, repositories) of different providers, and the Data Portal allows efficient search of and access to datasets across the integrated resources. The Data Portal services are provided openly and freely to all researchers and other users, such as heritage professionals, citizen scientists, students. The sections that follow first describe the enhancements of the ARIADNE data portal, which turned it into an effective research tool, followed by the current status of dataset ingest and portal access statistics.

4.4.2 Enhancement of the ARIADNE data portal

The core achievement of the original ARIADNE project was the implementation of a fully functional pipeline to harvest, integrate and make searchable on a portal data records from repositories and databases of institutions located in different countries. The pipeline aggregates the data records into the ARIADNE catalogue and feeds the search portal with records that are integrated based on common standards.

In ARIADNEplus the data portal has been enhanced in several ways. Firstly, the technical setup has been reworked and the data pipeline, catalogue and portal are now being hosted on the Cloud-based D4Science platform of CNR-ISTI. Secondly, after many enhancements by the SND team, the new data portal⁴⁰ offers advanced data search, visualisation and exploration facilities (on the technical implementation of the portal see ARIADNEplus 2022d: 15-22). The following list gives an overview of important enhancements from the user perspective:

- *Multi-lingual and granular subjects search*: since the large and multi-lingual Getty AAT is being used as the “hub” for the mapped subject terms of the data providers (see [Section 5.3.3](#)), the ARIADNE portal supports multi-lingual cross-searching of the data records. In an AAT terms-based search, results for available narrower terms are also included. Consequently, if a broad term such as “swords” is being used, records relating to more specific sub-categories are included in the search results, including where the respective terms are in other languages.

⁴⁰ ARIADNEplus data portal, <https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu>

Figure 1: Example illustrating the multi-lingual and granular search functionality of the ARIADNE data portal.

- **Map-based search:** The map-search facility now provides different layer types (Open Street Map, Open Topology, Google layers, e.g., satellite-view), heat maps and cluster points for results, polygon support for areas of interest, but also bounding boxes to mask precise location, direct links to identified resources of interest, and more.

Figure 2: Example illustrating polygon search on map of Shetland (using Google Satellite layer).

It is worth noting that the extra effort invested in the Map-based search facility has been informed by results of the ARIADNEplus user community needs survey, which showed a particularly high interest of researchers in location-based search of available data resources.

- **Timeline-search** based on time-spans and named cultural periods based on sets of periods provided by ARIADNE/plus partners and associates to the PeriodO system.
- **New and improved filters** such as the enlarged list of resource types, subjects of the Getty AAT covered, etc., and all filters can be applied to the results from both the Map and Timeline search facilities.
- **The resource landing pages** from portal searches have been improved with more features to find similar resources directly from these pages and they also include artefact images, where available.

4.4.3 The portal: an effective research tool

Use of different search filters of the data portal allows new types of research, for example for comparison of patterns of settlements or artefacts found in different regions relating to different cultural periods. Such research was not possible to achieve as effectively before.

The aggregated data and search functionalities may also enable the discovery of new sites, as illustrated by Julian Richards (ADS) with the example of 31 known Anglo-Saxon cemeteries in North Lincolnshire, UK, while public finds of Anglo-Saxon brooches point to over 400 interesting locations in the same area.

Through data integration and powerful search and visualisation services, the ARIADNE research e-infrastructure enables innovation in archaeological research methods. Geser (2020) argued that in addition to innovation in research methods there could be a gain in research efficiency through the enhanced access to data and online tools.

In the case of the Archaeology Data Service (ADS), a national-level data repository, the increase in the users' research efficiency has been calculated to be worth at least five times the costs of operation (Beagrie & Houghton 2013). Similar effects may be enabled by ARIADNEplus at the European level and

internationally by reducing researchers' effort to discover, combine and use shared research data. Actually, the new ARIADNE data portal supports these tasks in an integrated way.

Use of the portal software beyond ARIADNEplus

Archaeology Data Service (ADS) have decided to adopt the ARIADNE portal system for the primary ADS user interface to their collections, replacing their ArchSearch and Archives search over the next two years. The portal system will also be used in the large-scale "Unpath'd Waters"⁴¹ project which will aggregate marine heritage data from UK waters. In this undertaking, the ARIADNE data catalogue ontology (AO-Cat) will also be used.⁴² Unpath'd Waters is one of five arts & humanities flagship projects under the "Towards a National Collection" programme.

The software for the ARIADNEplus portal is publicly available on the GitHub code versioning system⁴³, and software packages for the whole ARIADNEplus virtual research environment (VRE) from the code repository of CNR-ISTI (ARIADNEplus 2022g).

⁴¹ Unpath'd Waters, <https://unpathdwaters.org.uk>

⁴² Information by ARIADNEplus deputy coordinator, Professor Julian Richards (UoY-ADS).

⁴³ ARIADNEplus portal software, <https://github.com/ARIADNE-Infrastructure/portal>

4.4.4 Integrated data records

At the close of the first ARIADNE project in January 2017, 16 data publishers had provided a total of 1,905,922 data records to the ARIADNE data portal. Meanwhile, the new portal provides access to **3,305,715** records from 31 publishers, integrated based on the advanced AO-Cat data model.

ARIADNE PORTAL	
▼ Publisher	
University of Patras	3
Consortium MASA - Mémoire des Archéologues et des Sites Archéologiques	9
University of Innsbruck	19
ICCD - Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo e la Documentazione	22
INFN	43
The Cyprus Institute	110
Institute of Archaeology Vasile Pârvan	136
Center for Digital Antiquity	171
Swedish National Data Service	484
Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil (LNEC)	1061
National Institute of Archaeology with Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	1952
IDACOR (CONICET/UNC)	2502
The Finnish Heritage Agency	3025
Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities	7517
CENIEH	8405
Aarhus University	8687
ZRC SAZU	8775
The Institute of Archaeology, Iceland	10344
International Association for Classical Archaeology	14279
National Heritage Institute - Romania	18279
THANADOS	23580
Swedish Rock Art Research Archives	25223
Institut national de recherches archéologiques préventives (Inrap)	37616
CEIPAC - Universitat de Barcelona	57089
Hungarian National Museum (HNM)	63019
Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)	99291
Nara National Research Institute for Cultural Properties	139368
Archaeological Information System of the Czech Republic (AIS CR)	229999
Historic Environment Scotland	334636
British Museum	945228
Archaeology Data Service	1124336

Some additional datasets have been prepared for aggregation in early 2023.

It must be noted that the number of records alone does not give an adequate account of the available content. In some cases, one record describes and directs the portal user to an accessible collection or archive, e.g., a fieldwork archive, which may contain from a few to hundreds of research objects (i.e., texts, images, data sheets, maps, GIS files, and others).

For example, of the records from University of Patras one describes and links to a dataset of radiocarbon dates for Aegean history and archaeology, 3159 radiocarbon samples from 353 sites, indeed, the largest collection so far of such data from Greece (Katsianis et al. 2020). Another record points to the Paliambela Kolindros survey archive, which contains data such as a digital terrain model of the site area, geological layers, geomagnetic survey data, 3D shapefiles for borehole location, geological layers and survey units, modern and past aerial images, landscape features, and more.

This is called collection-level access, while item-level records describe and link to a single content item, such as a fieldwork report. Thus, there are data collections from which each item can be found directly on the portal, while in other cases only indirectly by following a link in the record of the collection served by the portal.

This difference between item-level access versus collection-level access is due to the technical setup of some data collections which make it difficult to provide records of individual items. In other cases, it is preferable to provide access at a higher level, e.g., the description of a data collection, rather than individual items without required contextual information. Therefore, for each collection the best integration approach has to be defined, taking into account its content and technical setup.

Figure 5: List of data providers and records of the ARIADNE portal as of 22 December 2022.

4.4.5 Portal access statistics

The statistics for the new data portal start from January 2021, which is when the upgraded version was implemented, with the enhanced search facilities following in early February.

From January to November 2021 there was a total of 7,165 visitors to the portal. By 9 December 2022, this had increased to 32,000 visitors, an increase of 350%. The project dissemination has focused on bringing users to the Portal and this appears to have succeeded.

Figure 6: Portal visitor rate profile 01.01.2021–09.12.2022.

Spikes in portal visits, such as in March and September 2022, can be attributed to social media referrals (Twitter), e.g., on 15 September 2022 there were 300 visitors in one day, following the tweet by the Journal of Open Archaeology (JOAD):

Figure 7: Tweet by the Journal of Open Archaeology (JOAD) on 15 September 2022.

Over the last year, over 60% of the traffic to the data portal has originated from searches made through Google. Most of the remaining traffic sources are likely to be bookmarks with some direct URL entry as well. Other search engines such as Bing and Facebook have also contributed to the portal traffic.

Figure 8: Traffic sources to the data portal, January–December 2022.

The following map shows the geographical location of portal visitors for the last year. The top 10 countries from which visitors come to the portal are United Kingdom, United States, France, Bulgaria, Italy, Germany, Netherlands, Hungary, Cyprus, Australia. All, except Australia have data records in the portal which tends to suggest that the combined dissemination at project level and by the partners themselves, e.g., when datasets are released, is helping to attract new users. The visitor rates for the top countries have continued to increase for the last year.

Figure 9: Countries of portal visitors, January–December 2022.

4.4.6 Summary of results

The new ARIADNE Data Portal exploits the enhanced integration of knowledge-based data resources, i.e., resources described with the CRM-based data catalogue model (AO-Cat) and vocabularies of the domain of knowledge. The portal services are provided freely and openly to all users.

Integrated data records

At the close of the original ARIADNE project in January 2017, 16 data publishers had provided over 1.9 million data records to the portal. Meanwhile, the new portal provides access to over 3.3 million records from 31 publishers integrated based on the new AO-Cat data model. Some additional datasets have been prepared and will be aggregated in early 2023.

Portal access statistics

The statistics for the new data portal start from January 2021: From January to November 2021 there was a total of 7,165 visitors to the portal. By 9 December 2022, this had increased to 32,000 visitors, an increase of almost 350%.

The top 10 countries from which visitors come to the portal are United Kingdom, United States, France, Bulgaria, Italy, Germany, Netherlands, Hungary, Cyprus, Australia. All, except Australia have data records in the portal. The visitor rates for the top countries have continued to increase for the last year.

Enhanced search facilities

In ARIADNEplus, the portal has been enhanced in several ways to offer advanced data search, visualisation and exploration facilities.

The portal now provides multi-lingual and granular subjects search, which builds on the mapping of the “local” vocabularies of partners and associates to the Getty AAT. The Map-search facility offers many new features, including different layer types, heat maps and cluster points for results, polygon support for areas of interest, but also bounding boxes to mask precise location.

Various options for filtering data records can be applied to results of both the Map-search and Timeline-search facility. Furthermore, where available, images of artefacts are included in served data records.

Results of the community needs survey have been duly considered, for example, with the extra effort invested on the Map-search facility to support users’ high interest in location-based search of data resources.

The portal as an effective research tool

In ARIADNEplus the data portal has been turned into an effective research tool. Use of different search filters of the portal allows new types of research, for example to explore and compare patterns of settlements or of artefacts found in different regions relating to different cultural periods.

Such research was not possible to achieve as effectively before. It reduces the effort required by researchers to discover, combine and analyse data for comparative research.

Use of the portal software beyond ARIADNEplus

Archaeology Data Service (ADS) have decided to adopt the ARIADNE portal system for the primary ADS user interface to their collections. The portal system will also be used in the large-scale “Unpath’d Waters” project which will aggregate marine heritage data from UK waters.

4.5 New services and virtual research environments

4.5.1 Expectation and project approach

RI Programme expectation

[2] “New or more advanced research infrastructure services, enabling leading-edge or multidisciplinary research, are made available to a wider user community.”

Project approach

The new data portal is already an effective research tool which exploits the integrated data on the “what”, “where” and “when” of archaeological research objects, thereby new types of research can be conducted by using different search filters.

Furthermore, ARIADNEplus enhanced e-research services developed in the original ARIADNE project and added new ones. Among the steps beyond ARIADNE are Virtual Research Environments (VREs) for e-archaeology on the Cloud-based D4Science platform; VREs are intended to support research tasks beyond what the data portal already allows.

On a general note, providing research tools online in Cloud-based environments enables researchers to avoid investing effort to acquire, implement, maintain and upgrade them. Instead of dealing with IT issues, researchers can focus on their research questions and collaboration.

4.5.2 Enhanced and new research services

This section gives a brief overview of enhanced and new ARIADNE research services. The overview does not include the tool for mapping database schema to the CIDOC CRM (FORTH’ 3M Tool) and the tool for mapping local vocabulary terms to the Getty AAT (USW’s Vocabulary Matching Tool) (see [Section 4.3.3](#) and [Section 4.3.4](#)). Not included are also the advanced Space-Time Query Services, which are implemented in the Data Portal and enable users to explore research question by applying powerful search and filter options.

Overview of enhanced and new research services

What follows are brief descriptions of enhanced and new ARIADNE research services; technical details of the services are given in an available deliverable (ARIADNEplus 2022h). Use of some of the services, especially the Cloud-based Geoserver and Visual Media Service, has been explored in pilots for innovative applications (ARIADNEplus 2022e).

Cloud-based Geoserver: The CNR-ISTI Cloud-based Geoserver provides common geospatial/GIS functionality, for example, buffer definition, layer selection, proximity, viewshed analysis and so on. How to enhance with the Geoserver services of ARIADNE and of national partners has been investigated. A major development in this regard is the National Geoportal for Archaeology in Italy (see [Section 4.5.3](#)).

Archaeological Image Annotation: A specialised annotation tool for annotating archaeological objects which contain textual or symbolic information has been developed by the Archaeological Museum of Zagreb (AMZ) and the CNR-ISTI Visual Computing Lab. Among other functionalities, the Digital Autoptic Process (DAP) tool allows to annotate in a CIDOC CRM compliant way images of such objects, including reliable images for use with RTI⁴⁴ (Ponchio et al. 2018). Functionalities of the tool have been integrated in the advanced Visual Media Service (see below).

⁴⁴ Reflectance Transformation Images - RTI.

Vocabulary Annotation: A service has been developed by University of South-Wales' Hypermedia Research Group that enables subject annotations of archaeological texts with terms of different vocabularies, e.g., Linked Open Data (LOD) thesauri of the FISH Terminology Working Group for archaeological objects and sciences. The need for such an application in interdisciplinary projects was identified in a workshop on VRE use cases. It is a Python application to locate and tag terms within free text and to output suggested subject annotations in a range of formats. It is provided in the ARIADNEplus_Lab VRE (see [Section 4.5.3](#)) as a Jupyter notebook with guidance and examples.

Advanced Natural Language Processing (NLP): NLP tools and processing pipelines based on the General Architecture for Text Engineering (GATE) framework have been developed in ARIADNE by University of South-Wales' Hypermedia Research Group and applied on documents in English, Dutch and Swedish (Binding et al. 2018; Vlachidis & Tudhope 2016). The GATE NLP-based approach has been enhanced by partners in an EOSCpilot demonstrator (TEXTCROWD⁴⁵), with documents in Italian (Felicetti et al. 2018). The EOSCpilot tools have been implemented on the D4Science platform. Further development in ARIADNEplus focused on making the user interface and tools easy to use by researchers. Furthermore, the NLP and semantic annotation system INCEption⁴⁶ has been implemented as an additional solution. The advanced GATE-based NLP services have been used for extracting data from INRAP fieldwork reports in French. INCEption proved to be very useful for producing an annotated corpus for the extraction process (ARIADNEplus 2022e).

3D Documentation of Archaeological Sites: The EpHEMERA⁴⁷ system of the Science and Technology in Archaeology Research Center (STARC) of The Cyprus Institute allows users to visualise in 3D the layers of archaeological areas, excavations, buildings, and their related documentation (Abate et al. 2017). Specifically, the service supports the documentation, management and preservation of endangered archaeological and architectural heritage. Users can query the database system and retrieve metadata attached to every single virtual object, and extract geometric and morphological information. Some functionalities of the system have been integrated in the advanced VMS.

Advanced Visual Media Service (VMS): The original ARIADNE VMS⁴⁸ already allowed users effective publication, rendering and exploration of enhanced images (e.g., Reflectance Transformation Imaging - RTI), and high-quality 3D models of buildings and artefacts. In ARIADNEplus, the CNR-IST VCLab has enhanced the VMS in several respects of which the most important is arguably enabling users to link information to selected parts of a 3D model. The VMS has thus become a virtual research environment. An ongoing development aims to make the VMS ready to effectively handle LiDAR data using specific visualization algorithms. The main users of the VMS so far are university-based creators of 3D models and applications. Many have also used it for academic courses and work for a master degree or PhD. In ARIADNEplus, the VMS have also been presented to cultural heritage institutions and businesses which support them in the creation of products, and collected their interest and requirements for using the service (see [Section 4.8](#)).

4.5.3 VRE use cases and development

VRE basic concept

Virtual Research Environments (VREs) are one of the most ambitious innovation goals of ARIADNEplus in the field of archaeological research. A VRE can generally be defined as an online working environment for a community of researchers that provides services and tools for research tasks. The

⁴⁵ TEXTCROWD (EOSCpilot demonstrator), <https://eoscipilot.eu/science-demos/textcrowd>

⁴⁶ INCEption (Ubiquitous Knowledge Processing Lab, TU Darmstadt), <https://inception-project.github.io>

⁴⁷ EpHEMERA, <http://ephemera.cyi.ac.cy>

⁴⁸ Visual Media Service <https://visual.ariadne-infrastructure.eu>

ARIADNEplus VREs build on services described in the previous section and are intended to support research tasks beyond what the data portal already allows.

The CNR-ISTI D4Science platform is being used for the VREs, as it provides VREs-as-a-service to support open science practices (Assante et al. 2016; Assante et al. 2019). VREs-as-a-service provide generic services (e.g., user authentication & authorization, communication, data storage, metadata, etc.), as well as services for different data types (text, tabular data, image, 3D) and data processing, visualisation and analysis. Related services for ARIADNEplus for example include CIDOC CRM and Vocabulary Mapping, Natural Language Processing, Visual Media Service and the ARIADNEplus_Lab.

VRE use cases workshops

Most archaeologists are not familiar with or even aware of VREs as developed by ARIADNEplus, and technological VRE developers with an archaeological background are rare as well. Therefore, “a bicycle made for two” approach (Pollard & Bray 2007) is necessary, in which archaeologists and technology experts learn from each other in a process of co-designing relevant and fit for purpose VREs.

In order to promote this process, three VRE use cases workshops have been organised with participation of researchers and developers, including external experts. The purpose of the workshops was to enable the archaeological research communities represented in ARIADNEplus to think about which data-related research tasks could be supported by VRE services, and to identify related general and domain-specific requirements.

The first two workshops involved VRE experts and archaeological researchers in four thematic domains represented in ARIADNEplus: Geospatial and Mortuary Data and Research (28 January 2021, 52 participants), and Ancient DNA and Environmental Data and Research (6 May 2021, 22 participants).

Existing VRE-like systems were also presented and discussed in the workshops: Thanados⁴⁹ in the field of mortuary archaeology, dataARC⁵⁰, which supports interdisciplinary research on human-environment interactions in the North Atlantic region, and the Strategic Environmental Archaeology Database (SEAD)⁵¹. Subsequently, Thanados and dataARC became associate partners of ARIADNEplus, while the collaboration with SEAD existed before. The presentations, discussion and conclusions of these workshops are summarised in the ARIADNEplus Final Report on Community Needs (ARIADNEplus 2021b: 52-67).

The third workshop focused on innovative pilots in which geospatial data infrastructure and services for remote-sensing data (e.g., LiDAR), GIS and other data resources play a major role (23 February 2022, 23 participants; ARIADNEplus 2022a). A core service in this regard is the Cloud-based Geoserver (see below).

Needs identified and addressed

In the VRE use cases workshops some needs were identified which subsequently have been addressed by developing or enhancing VRE services. As a general need, dataARC co-developer Rachel Opitz (University of Glasgow) emphasised that design principles of VRE services and support should take into account the concerns of researchers regarding data sharing and reuse in VREs (see also the paper on dataARC by Opitz et al. 2021). Other expressed needs and solutions are, in brief:

ARIADNEplus_Lab VRE: The definition of searches over large and varied datasets, their execution and analysis may require a VRE and appropriate computing resources, as experienced by SEAD director,

⁴⁹ Thanados - The Anthropological and Archaeological Database of Sepultures, <https://thanados.net>

⁵⁰ dataARC – Enabling Research on the Long-Term Human Ecodynamics of the North Atlantic, www.data-arc.org

⁵¹ SEAD - Strategic Environmental Archaeology Database, www.sead.se

Phil Buckland, Umeå University. For these purposes, the D4Science team developed the ARIADNEplus_Lab VRE⁵² which offers researchers a set of tools to process, visualise and analyse ARIADNE, as well as own data (Pagano 2022). The tools include JupyterHub (pre-installed and ready to use), RStudio and the DataMiner analytics engine to specify and execute data computing tasks on the D4Science Cloud-based infrastructure. The virtual research lab also provides access to the ARIADNEplus Linked Open Data (LOD).

GraphDB - ARIADNEplus Linked Open Data (LOD): The ARIADNEplus LOD, which includes all data providers' records modelled according to the ARIADNE Ontology, is being managed with the GraphDB semantic graph database. Through GraphDB, researchers can explore the LOD with the available web GUI or programmatically with SPARQL queries (W3C 2013). Access to the GraphDB and documentation is provided by the ARIADNEplus_Lab. Documentation is available as a Python notebook, a PDF file or in Markdown format.⁵³ The Python notebook can be run on the JupyterHub tool available in the ARIADNEplus_Lab. The guide also contains examples of queries that can be run on the ARIADNEplus LOD.

Annotation of research objects with different domain vocabularies: In interdisciplinary research scholars often have different views of research objects and could jointly benefit from semantic annotations of the objects with terms of different vocabularies. This need was identified in the discussion of the interdisciplinary dataARC platform. A service that supports the purpose for archaeological texts has been developed (see [Section 4.5.2](#)). For annotations of visual content, researchers can use functionalities of the ARIADNEplus VMS.

Visual Media Service (VMS): The VMS now includes the capability to link information on a 3D model and selected parts of it for research documentation, as well as other purposes, e.g., museum information about cultural artefacts. A visual wizard has been defined to guide VMS users to easily add hotspots and interactive links from the 3D model to the related documentation. Thereby, the VMS has become a VRE going beyond the standard services for effective publishing and rendering 3D model for interactive exploration.

VREs based on the Geoserver: A major VRE that is being developed by the D4Science team for ARIADNEplus partner ICCU and the Istituto Centrale per l'Archeologia (ICA) is the National Geoportal for Archeology (GNA) (ARIADNEplus (2022i: 20-23). The GNA will provide map-based access to data from archaeological work carried out based on ministerial concessions. The portal will be a significant advance in the access to archaeological data in Italy (Calandra et al. 2021; Acconcia et al. 2022). Use of the Geoserver has also been explored in a pilot VRE for research on the Esquiline area of Rome (ARIADNEplus 2022e; ARIADNEplus 2022i: 27-28).

4.5.4 Summary of results

Enhanced and new research services

While the Data Portal already provides an effective research tool, ARIADNEplus also enhanced e-research services developed in the original ARIADNE project and added new ones to the portfolio of services and VREs.

Natural Language Processing (NLP) services originally developed in ARIADNE have been enhanced and applied to documents in additional European languages.

⁵² ARIADNEplus_Lab VRE (CNR ISTI), https://ariadne.d4science.org/web/ariadneplus_lab/ (new users have to register the first time they access ARIADNEplus on D4Science)

⁵³ GraphDB user guide (CNR ISTI, Bardi A. et al.), <https://data.d4science.net/EvVX>

A service for subject annotations of archaeological texts with terms of different vocabularies has been developed in response to a need for such annotations in interdisciplinary research projects.

Services for the visualisation and annotation of images and 3D models have been enhanced, including the Digital Autoptic Process (DAP) service for annotations in a CIDOC CRM compliant way of archaeological objects which contain textual or symbolic information, and EpHEMERA for 3D documentation of archaeological sites. Functionalities of these services have been included in the Visual Media Service (VMS).

The original ARIADNE VMS already allowed users effective publication, rendering and exploration of enhanced images (e.g., Reflectance Transformation Imaging - RTI) and high-quality 3D models of buildings and artefacts. In ARIADNEplus, the VMS has been enhanced in several respects, the most important of which is enabling users to link information to selected parts of a 3D model. A visual wizard is included which guides VMS users to easily add such hotspots and interactive links to the related documentation.

Virtual Research Environments (VREs)

Virtual Research Environments (VREs) are one of the most ambitious innovation goals of ARIADNEplus in the field of archaeological research. VREs combine and tailor services for research tasks and data of research communities.

In ARIADNEplus Cloud-based VRE services implemented on the D4Science platform are intended to support research tasks beyond what the data portal already allows. Use of some of the services, especially the Geoserver and Visual Media Service, has been explored in pilots for innovative applications.

To kick-start the VRE development, three use cases workshop were organised focused on thematic domains represented in ARIADNEplus, including Geospatial, Environmental, Mortuary and ancient DNA data and research. Developers of dataARC and Thanados, which thereafter became associate partners of ARIADNEplus, were among the external participants. During the workshops, some of the researchers' needs were identified and addressed by developing or enhancing VRE services.

The *ARIADNEplus_Lab VRE* offers researchers a set of tools to process, visualise and analyse ARIADNE, as well as own data. The tools include JupyterHub (pre-installed and ready to use), RStudio and the DataMiner analytics engine to specify and execute data computing tasks on the D4Science Cloud-based infrastructure.

The virtual research lab also provides researchers access to the *ARIADNEplus Linked Open Data (LOD)* in the semantic graph database (GraphDB), and tools for exploring the LOD with an available web GUI or programmatically, using SPARQL queries.

The aforementioned new service for subject annotations of archaeological texts with terms of different vocabularies has been added to the *ARIADNEplus_Lab VRE*.

VREs have also been developed building on the Cloud-based Geoserver. A major development is the National Geoportal for Archaeology in Italy, which will provide map-based access to data from archaeological fieldwork. Use of the Geoserver has also been explored in a pilot VRE for research on the Esquilina area of Rome.

Enhancements of the *Visual Media Service (VMS)*, particularly the capability to add hotspots and interactive links to documentation to 3D models, have turned it into a research environment. It is also relevant for other purposes, e.g., museum information about cultural artefacts in 3D.

Finally, it is worth highlighting that research tools which are available online in Cloud-based environments enable researchers to avoid investing efforts to acquire, implement, maintain and upgrade

them. Instead of dealing with IT issues, the researchers can focus on their research questions and collaboration.

4.6 Research infrastructures coordination

4.6.1 Expectation and project approach

RI Programme expectation

[3] *“Operators of related infrastructures develop synergies and complementary capabilities, leading to improved and harmonised services. There is less duplication of services, leading to an improved use of resources across Europe. Economies of scale and saving of resources are also realised due to common development and the optimisation of operations.”*

“Digital services developed under the joint research activities should be exposed under the EOSC catalogue”, statement in section “Specific features for Research Infrastructures” of the RI Programme, Part D, (iii): Joint Research Activities.

Project approach

The goal here is to contribute to the coordination among related research e-Infrastructures in order to enable synergies through joint development, optimisation and combination of complementary capabilities. Already fostered, coordination by the original ARIADNE project with other major research infrastructures, particularly their e-Infrastructure component, has carried on regarding harmonised data models (e.g., data catalogues), application of the CIDOC CRM ontology and common domain vocabularies. This promotes integration of data and saving of resources through re-use of knowledge assets.

However, the overall strategy of ARIADNEplus regarding improved use of resources, economies of scale and cost-savings is now a Cloud-based virtualisation and integration in the European Open Science Cloud - EOSC (Richards & Niccolucci 2019: 23). Therefore, ARIADNEplus prepared registration of its portfolio of Cloud-based services in the EOSC catalogue of resources. This will allow other research e-Infrastructures in the EOSC eco-system to use complementary ARIADNEplus services relevant for their operation, and *vice versa*.

ARIADNEplus aims for full integration into the EOSC and, depending on the functionality provided, joint development of digital services with providers of related fields (e.g., heritage sciences, cultural history and other humanities).

4.6.2 Coordination areas and activities

Coordination with related e-Infrastructures in the field of humanities and heritage research started in the original ARIADNE project through networking with the major European projects already active at that time: CENDARI, the ESFRI Roadmap initiatives CLARIN and DARIAH, and Europeana.

CENDARI built an e-Infrastructure for historical archives⁵⁴; CLARIN connects language resources and tools into a central platform; DARIAH focuses on supporting digital practices of scholars in a wide range of arts and humanities domains (tools, methods, training). The knowledge exchange with Europeana focuses on common topics related to making digital/digitised cultural heritage content, including archaeology content, accessible.

⁵⁴ Unfortunately, the CENDARI - Collaborative European Digital Archive Infrastructure project (2012-2016), with a focus on digital archives for the Medieval and World War I eras, was not continued.

Close relations also exist with the research infrastructure E-RIHS for heritage science, which has been included in the ESFRI Roadmap in 2016; and with the Competence Centre on the Conservation of Cultural Heritage (4CH), which develops a virtual competence centre using Cloud-based ICT infrastructure to provide services and support to cultural heritage institutions. The ARIADNE initiative also aims to support the ambitious goals of the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) initiative.

Overall, today the main common point of coordination between research infrastructures, particularly their e-Infrastructure component, is the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative.

Standardisation of data catalogues

A major strand of joint development has been CIDOC CRM based models for catalogues of humanities and heritage data resources. The initial model created by ARIADNE for archaeology has been taken up by the PARTHENOS⁵⁵ humanities and social sciences e-Infrastructures cluster project (which included the European platforms CLARIN and DARIAH, and leading national institutions).

In turn, the PARTHENOS CRMpe catalogue model (Frosini et al. 2018) has been developed further by ARIADNEplus with the new AO-Cat (ARIADNE Object Catalogue). Although it has advanced considerably, the model still allows the alignment of digital humanities, archaeology and heritage science data catalogue models, enabling synergies between different research infrastructures and domains of research (see *Section 4.3.2*).

ARIADNEplus and E-RIHS

ARIADNEplus is closely allied to E-RIHS⁵⁶, the distributed European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science. Several partners were already involved in the preparatory phase of E-RIHS (E-RIHS PP)⁵⁷, e.g., the ARIADNEplus coordinator PIN (Italy), CYI-STARC (Cyprus), CENIEH (Spain), DANS (Netherlands), IAA (Israel), and LNEC (Portugal), among others.

Particularly relevant for ARIADNEplus are scientific data from advanced methods of material analyses and conservation of artifacts. As some ARIADNEplus partners employ such methods, the CIDOC CRM application profile CRMhs (heritage science) was created, and it can also be used for the E-RIHS DIGILAB component (Castelli & Felicetti 2018; Castelli et al. 2021).

The first showcase implementation of the CRMhs profile will be the new scientific data repository of the ARIADNEplus partner INFN, which is currently being developed. INFN datasets based on the general ARIADNE catalogue model are already included in the data portal.⁵⁸

ARIADNEplus and Europeana

The growing importance of 3D content, use of Cloud-based solutions, and the adoption of the FAIR principles by cultural heritage institutions are among the common topics of ARIADNEplus and Europeana. These were already strongly present in an EOSC-focused workshop and sessions of the Europeana Conference 2019 (November 2019), with chairs and contributions of ARIADNEplus partners CARARE, ICCU and PIN (EOSC Secretariat 2019; Europeana 2019).

Project partner CARARE is the main liaison of ARIADNEplus with Europeana with regards to the archaeology theme. CARARE is an aggregator for Europeana and, among other content, they have also provided many archaeology-related items. Exploring common approaches for connecting user groups

⁵⁵ PARTHENOS (H2020, 5/2015-10/2019), <http://www.parthenos-project.eu>

⁵⁶ E-RIHS - European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science, <http://www.e-rihs.eu>

⁵⁷ E-RIHS PP (2/2017-9/2020), <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/739503>

⁵⁸ INFN dataset records, <https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/publisher/infnpublisher=INFN>

such as students, educators and citizen science projects with archaeological content resources (see [Section 4.9](#)) is particularly relevant for ARIADNEplus, and an exemplary project in this regard has been Europeana Archaeology⁵⁹, with participation of the ARIADNEplus partners DANS, ICCU and INP.

ARIADNEplus and 4CH

ARIADNEplus has close ties with the Competence Centre on the Conservation of Cultural Heritage (4CH)⁶⁰ project which aims to provide expertise and solutions for cultural heritage conservation, preservation and valorisation through digital technologies, with a focus on 3D technologies. The project is being coordinated by ARIADNEplus partner INFN and nine other partners are among the consortium of 19 organisations. 4CH develops a virtual competence centre using Cloud-based ICT infrastructure to provide services and support to cultural heritage institutions.

Supporting the ECCCH

The ARIADNE initiative supports the ambitious goals of the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) initiative. Summarised by Commissioner Mariya Gabriel, *“Europe’s rich cultural heritage will enter a new digital dimension with the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage. This European effort will facilitate cooperation between researchers, curators and museum professionals in order to safeguard our cultural heritage, enable easy access to cultural content and allow future generations to enjoy it for years to come. It will also offer new opportunities to smaller museums and cultural institutions to advance digitisation and work together on joint projects in secure and highly professional working space”* (European Commission 2022c).

The recent ex-ante impact assessment of the ECCCH initiative recognised ARIADNEplus as an important related research infrastructure, enabling to reach the archaeological domain, and providing essential insights into what is needed for FAIR cultural heritage data (European Commission 2022d: 22, 26 and 60). *“Producing FAIR metadata is a key challenge if we want to publish and enrich European Cultural Heritage on the Web that originates from different countries, diverse Cultural Heritage domains, and is represented by mutually incompatible metadata models, written in different languages. This is a lesson learned, for example, in the massive Europeana.eu initiative, and in more domain-specific projects, such as ARIADNEplus for archaeology”* (European Commission 2022d: 60).

In the years 2023 to 2025, the European Commission, through Horizon Europe, plans to invest € 110 million on projects for the Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage. The ARIADNE initiative looks forward to supporting the ECCCH with its expertise in Cloud-based data and research services developed for the archaeological domain.

European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a pan-European vision and initiative aimed to provide Cloud-based infrastructure services for researchers across Europe that enable the storage, management, analysis and re-use of research data compliant with the FAIR principles.

The EOSC provides a common strategy and virtual platform for research e-Infrastructures to enable use of shared resources, economies of scale and cost-savings in the development and operation of e-Infrastructures. ARIADNEplus aims for full integration into the EOSC and, depending on the functionality provided, joint development of digital services with providers of related fields, e.g., heritage sciences, cultural history and other humanities).

⁵⁹ Europeana Archaeology, <https://europeanaarchaeology.carare.eu>

⁶⁰ 4CH (EU H2020, 01/2021-12/2023), <https://www.4ch-project.eu>

Therefore, ARIADNEplus has prepared the registration of its portfolio of Cloud-based services in the EOSC Marketplace (catalogue of resources). This will allow other research e-Infrastructures in the EOSC eco-system use complementary ARIADNEplus services relevant for their operation, and *vice versa*.

Some Cloud-based services provided by CNR-ISTI for ARIADNEplus can already be found in the EOSC Marketplace, for example, the Visual Media Service VRE⁶¹ and the more generic RPrototypingLab VRE⁶² and Jupyter Hub⁶³, which are being used for the ARIADNEplus_Lab (see [Section 4.5.3](#)). There is also a platform-level integration of the D4Science platform with the EOSC which allows to connect the ARIADNEplus part of D4Science with the EOSC (e.g., through federated identity services) in a transparent way.

In June 2022, EOSC released the Resource Data Model (also called Resource Profile) to production, which is to be used for new research IT services. A mapping of the services part of the ARIADNE catalogue model (AO-Cat) to the EOSC Resource Data Model has been created, so that services described in the ARIADNE catalogue are discoverable along with services of e-Infrastructures of other communities federated by EOSC (ARIADNEplus 2022h: 8-12; Appendix A of this deliverable provides the template for the EOSC compliant service description).

4.6.3 Summary of results

Coordination with related e-Infrastructures

Coordination with related e-Infrastructures in the field of humanities and heritage research started in the original ARIADNE project through networking with the major European projects already active at that time: CENDARI (e-Infrastructure for historical archives), CLARIN (language resources and tools), DARIAH (arts & humanities tools, methods, training), and Europeana.

The growing importance of 3D content, use of Cloud-based solutions, and the adoption of the FAIR principles by cultural heritage institutions are among the common topics with Europeana developer groups. An additional important topic concerns common approaches for connecting different user groups with archaeological content resources.

Close relations exist with the research infrastructure E-RIHS for heritage science, as several partners were already involved in the preparatory phase of this ESFRI Roadmap initiative. Particularly relevant for ARIADNEplus are scientific data from advanced methods of material analyses and conservation of artifacts. As some ARIADNEplus partners employ such methods, the CIDOC CRM application profile CRMhs (heritage science) was created, which can also be used for the E-RIHS DIGILAB component.

The first showcase implementation of the CRMhs profile will be the new scientific data repository of ARIADNEplus partner INFN, which is currently being developed. INFN datasets based on the general CIDOC CRM-based ARIADNE catalogue model are already included in the data portal.

ARIADNEplus has also close ties with the Competence Centre on the Conservation of Cultural Heritage project (4CH, coordinated by INFN) which develops a virtual competence centre using Cloud-based ICT infrastructure to provide services and support to cultural heritage institutions.

⁶¹ D4Science Infrastructure: Visual Media Service VRE, <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/visual-media-service-virtual-research-environment>

⁶² D4Science Infrastructure: RPrototypingLab VRE, <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/rprototypinglab-virtual-research-environment>

⁶³ D4Science Infrastructure: Jupyter Hub, <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/jupyter-hub>

Connecting with EOSC

Today, the main common point of coordination between research infrastructures, particularly their e-Infrastructure component, is the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative.

Therefore, ARIADNEplus prepared the registration of its portfolio of Cloud-based services in the EOSC Marketplace (catalogue of resources). This will allow other research e-Infrastructures in the EOSC ecosystem use complementary ARIADNEplus services relevant for their operation, and *vice versa*.

Some Cloud-based services provided by CNR-ISTI for ARIADNEplus through the D4Science platform can already be found in the EOSC Marketplace. However, in June 2022 EOSC released the Resource Data Model to production which is to be used for research IT services.

A mapping of the services part of the ARIADNE catalogue model (AO-Cat) to the EOSC Resource Data Model has been created, so that services described in the ARIADNE catalogue are discoverable along with services of e-Infrastructures of other communities federated by EOSC.

It is also worth noting that a platform-level integration of the D4Science platform with the EOSC exists which allows connecting the ARIADNEplus part of D4Science with the EOSC (e.g., through federated identity services) in a transparent way.

The ARIADNE initiative also aims to support the ambitious goals of the recently launched European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) initiative. The ex-ante impact assessment of the ECCCH recognised ARIADNEplus as an important related research infrastructure, enabling to reach the archaeological domain, and providing essential insights into what is needed for FAIR cultural heritage data.

4.7 Cross-disciplinary fertilisation and sharing of resources

4.7.1 Expectation and project approach

RI Programme expectation

[6] *“Closer interactions between larger number of researchers active in and around a number of infrastructures facilitate cross-disciplinary fertilisations and a wider sharing of information, knowledge and technologies across fields and between academia and industry.”*

Project approach

Large-scale, single-sited research infrastructures may promote cross-disciplinary fertilisation, as scholars from different backgrounds visit and use their special instruments (e.g., synchrotrons, advanced spectroscopy, etc.), exchange ideas and maybe start a joint project.

In the ARIADNE research e-Infrastructure initiative, cross-disciplinary fertilisation has been promoted by the participation of research groups and the sharing of datasets from different fields of archaeological research. ARIADNEplus extended the cross-fertilisation potential further by incorporating many more archaeological research communities, including those using natural sciences techniques, i.e., archaeometrical and biological research methods.

More specifically, cross-fertilisation is being fostered by the common objective of research groups to share and integrate data to enable comparative and interdisciplinary research. This requires use of appropriate data models (e.g., CIDOC CRM based models) and domain vocabularies, which allow interlinking and exploitation of shared data based on Linked Data methods and technologies.

Strong cross-fertilisation is also being fostered between scholars and developers of e-research services, for example in the VRE use cases workshops in which service developers learned about the requirements of scholars' projects, and scholars learned how VREs could support their research tasks.

Furthermore, collaboration with external developers is enabled specifically with developers of Linked Data applications, who can access and build on the ARIADNEplus Linked Open Data (LOD).

The aspect of sharing information, knowledge and technologies more widely between academia and industry is addressed in the next *Section 4.8* on innovation through partnership with industry. In general, all ARIADNEplus services are available for use also by businesses active in archaeology and cultural heritage, e.g., service providers for preventive archaeology and heritage management. The same applies to cultural and creative businesses which may benefit especially from using the Visual Media Service (VMS) to create products for museums, monuments and sites.

4.7.2 Cross-fertilisation areas and activities

Cross-fertilisation has been fostered in the building of CIDOC CRM application profiles, takes place in the development of VRE use cases, and is also being promoted through joint use of ARIADNEplus Linked Open Data (LOD).

Building of CRM application profiles

Cross-disciplinary fertilisation has been promoted in the effort to create CIDOC CRM application profiles for data of different domains of archaeological research in ARIADNEplus (see *Section 4.3.5*), for example heritage science (e.g., material studies and dating), ancient DNA, mortuary archaeology, and studies of ancient texts such as epigraphy.

Using the CIDOC CRM as the common conceptual basis, the development of the application profiles for the integration of different domain databases contributed to building common understanding and cross-fertilisation. Differences and communalities became clearer in the process.

Development of VRE use cases

Cross-disciplinary fertilisation has also been promoted in the development of ARIADNEplus virtual research environments (VREs) for archaeological research communities (see *Section 4.5.3*). The VREs must be co-designed by scholars and technical experts. In the co-design process, the technologists can understand better the research purposes and requirements of the scholars, while the scholars can learn how VRE services and tools can support their research tasks.

Particularly challenging is building VREs for interdisciplinary research based on data resources integrated for comparative research and synthesis, as exemplified by the dataARC VRE for research on long-term human ecodynamics, or initiatives such as the Coalition for Archaeological Synthesis (CfAS, founded in 2017).

CfAS promotes research projects to address major cross-disciplinary research questions which must be tackled with aggregated large and varied datasets and effective VRE services. ARIADNE is a CfAS member providing data integration and search capability and *“supports archaeological synthesis by enabling researchers to distillate relevant information from archaeological digital data”* (CfAS⁶⁴).

⁶⁴ CfAS: Coalition partners: ARIADNE, <https://www.archsynth.org/about/partners/>

Joint use of ARIADNEplus Linked Open Data

In ARIADNEplus the data records of the different providers are harmonised, aggregated and transformed to the Linked Data format RDF. The data in this format are integrated in the ARIADNEplus semantic graph database (GraphDB) which is the basis for the services of the Data Portal.

The graph database is also accessible to external developers through the ARIADNEplus_Lab VRE which provides tools for exploring the Linked Open Data (LOD) with an available web GUI or programmatically using SPARQL queries. This will enable cross-fertilisation at the data-level and among application developers. Developers can explore the LOD and seek to link it with data of other projects (see [Section 4.3.6](#) and [Section 4.5.3](#)).

An ARIADNEplus LOD hackathon was organised on 29/30 November 2022 at the biannual Linked Past conference hosted by UoY-ADS in York (UK). The conference brings together the community interested in LOD as applied to the study of the ancient and historical world, for example the Pelagios Network. The hackathon featured the ARIADNE data portal and LOD, and challenged 15 participants to explore them for addressing research questions.

It is also worth noting that provision of datasets to ARIADNEplus to produce Linked Data is not a one-way street. Data providers can get their datasets back, but transformed to the semantic web standard RDF. Thus, they can use it for other purposes, for instance linking it to external resources. This can also be done in the ARIADNEplus RDF database, hence partners do not need to set up an own triple store.

4.7.3 Summary of results

In the ARIADNE research e-Infrastructure initiative cross-disciplinary fertilisation is being promoted by the participation of research groups and the sharing of datasets from different fields of archaeological research, which has been greatly extended by ARIADNEplus.

Cross-fertilisation is particularly being fostered by the common objective of research groups to share and integrate data to enable comparative and interdisciplinary research, which ARIADNEplus supports through advancing the semantic interoperability of data resources.

CIDOC CRM application profiles, with a common CRM core and extensions for datasets of different archaeological domains, could play an important role in future cross-disciplinary research. In ARIADNEplus, the work on such application profiles has significantly contributed to building common understanding and cross-fertilisation. Different and common aspects of domain datasets became clearer in the process.

Cross-fertilisation has also been fostered between scholars and developers of e-research services in the ARIADNEplus VRE use cases workshops. VREs must be co-designed by scholars and technical experts. In the process service developers learn about the requirements of scholars' projects, while scholars learn how VREs can support their research tasks.

Collaboration and cross-fertilisation with external developers is enabled based on the ARIADNEplus Linked Open Data (LOD), which is accessible through a dedicated VRE. The ARIADNEplus_Lab VRE provides tools for exploring and building on the LOD, i.e., and link it with data of other projects.

4.8 Innovation and partnership with industry

4.8.1 Expectation and project approach

Programme expectation

[4] *“Innovation is fostered through a reinforced partnership of research organisations with industry.”*

Project approach

The notion of industrial innovation of the Research Infrastructures (RI) Programme is informed by RIs in fields such as energy, materials or life sciences research and development. In these fields, innovation may result from advances in the construction of RIs involving industrial providers of components (e.g., procurement of innovative instrumentation), joint R&D projects, or the use of experimental facilities by industrial researchers and developers (ESFRI Innovation Working Group 2018).

In archaeology, private sector commercial actors are businesses of contract archaeologists and consultancies, which provide professional services for developers and heritage management agencies in preventive archaeology. In some European countries, such contract archaeology has become the dominant form of field archaeology (e.g., in the Netherlands and the UK), while in others (semi-)public institutions play a greater role (e.g., ARIADNEplus partner INRAP in France).

Archaeological businesses, often spin-offs or otherwise related to archaeological research centres (i.e., as a charitable trust), can benefit from using ARIADNEplus services and datasets, but may also share fieldwork reports and data through underlying repositories. Making such reports and data accessible together with academic studies can allow all actors to benefit from a common source of information.

This means that partnership and collaboration on such information has to be promoted by national or regional authorities and implemented in their data management system or recommended repositories. This has happened in the Netherlands and UK, where DANS and ADS are mandated repositories. In other countries, heritage authorities receive fieldwork documentation from preventive archaeology, but access to it is often limited to authorised user, i.e., cultural heritage administrators, registered archaeologists and consultants.

In ARIADNEplus, innovation in this field focuses on using Cloud-based Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies to extract information from grey literature reports of preventive archaeology for metadata which can be used to enhance access to such reports.

Furthermore, cultural and creative businesses have been identified as potential users of the ARIADNEplus Cloud-based Visual Media Services, particularly businesses which create products for museums, monuments and sites.

4.8.2 Selected innovation areas

The main innovation areas considered concern the ARIADNEplus Cloud-based Natural Language Processing (NLP) services and the Visual Media Service (VMS).

Cloud-based NLP services

Archaeological businesses can benefit from using ARIADNEplus services and datasets, but may also share fieldwork reports through accessible repositories. Making such reports accessible along with academic studies can allow all actors to benefit from a common source of information.

In ARIADNEplus innovation in this field focused on using Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies to extract information from fieldwork reports for metadata which can be used to enhance access to such reports.

Experimental work on this started in the original ARIADNE project, with promising results for reports in English, Dutch and Swedish. Building on the GATE NLP framework, different Named Entity Recognition (NER) techniques were applied using vocabularies and annotated text corpora as training data for machine-learning algorithms (Binding et al. 2018; Vlachidis & Tudhope 2016).

Further developments have been carried out in TEXTCROWD⁶⁵, which was an EOSCpilot demonstrator of innovative capabilities provided by Cloud-based solutions. Again, Named Entity Recognition based on vocabularies and with annotated text corpora was executed but with the NLP management interface and processing pipeline Cloud-based on the D4Science platform of CNR-ISTI instead of on a desktop computer. In this project, fieldwork reports in Italian language have been processed (Felicetti et al. 2018).

Further development in ARIADNEplus of the Cloud-based NLP services focused on making the user interface and tools easy to use by researchers. In the project, the advanced NLP services have also been used for extracting data from INRAP fieldwork reports in French (ARIADNEplus 2022e).

Cloud-based Visual Media Services

During the COVID-19 crisis, many closed-down museums, monuments and sites resorted to using social media platforms (e.g., Twitter, Instagram, Facebook) and, where available, digital content collections, virtual museum exhibitions and tours. It became clear that, to be prepared for future demand, new and more attractive products are needed, for instance educational content with 3D models of artefacts (see [Section 4.1.4](#)).

However, a report of the Europeana 3D Content Task Force (2020) showed that advanced 3D content solutions have not reached many institutions so far. 3D content, where available, often means videos of objects, while 3D models that can be directly and meaningfully used are rare. The availability of more functional and high-quality 3D content should be supported.

Therefore, the ARIADNE Visual Media Service (VMS)⁶⁶ is considered relevant for cultural heritage institutions and creative businesses which support the creation of products for museums, monuments and sites based on 3D models and other imagery. The VMS enable easy publication, visualisation and exploration of high-resolution 3D models and Reflectance Transformation Images (RTI). In ARIADNEplus, the capability to link information to selected parts of a 3D model was developed. A visual wizard is included which guides VMS users to easily add such hotspots and interactive links to related documentation (see [Section 4.5.2](#)).

The CNR-ISTI VCLab team and ICCU have presented the advanced VMS in a webinar to businesses and heritage institutions to explore existing demand and requirements for using the service (4 April 2022, approx. 50 participants). Among the perceived “selling points” of the VMS are confidentiality, support of high-resolution interactive media, and the capability to make it accessible with related information on the presented objects.

Users have full control of the data that is being uploaded for processing by the VMS. After the conversion for multiresolution streaming and visualisation, the user can download the entire viewer (webpage, scripts and data), completely removing it from the VSM, and use it on their own web server. Institutions that are less concerned about control of access, may also leave the product on the VMS

⁶⁵ TEXTCROWD (EOSCpilot demonstrator): <https://eoscpilot.eu/science-demos/textcrowd>

⁶⁶ Visual Media Service (CNR-ISTI, Visual Computing Lab), <https://visual.ariadne-infrastructure.eu>

for access and maintenance. VMS-supported products are usually high-resolution with a viewer for direct and meaningful interaction. In addition, the capability to link information to highlighted parts of a 3D model makes it possible to add descriptive and narrative text to the model.

4.8.3 Summary of results

In archaeology, private sector commercial actors are businesses of contract archaeologists and consultancies which provide professional services for developers and heritage management agencies in preventive archaeology.

Archaeological businesses, often spin-offs or otherwise related to archaeological research centres, can benefit from using ARIADNEplus services and datasets, but may also share fieldwork reports through underlying repositories. Such sharing must be promoted by national or regional authorities and implemented in their data management system or mandated repositories, as in the case of ADS in the UK and DANS in the Netherlands.

In ARIADNEplus innovation in this field focused on using Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies to extract information from fieldwork reports for metadata which can be used to enhance access to such reports. Building on foundational work in the original ARIADNE project and an EOSCpilot project, further development in ARIADNEplus focused on improving the Cloud-based NLP solution and applying it to extract data from fieldwork reports of INRAP in French.

The Cloud-based Visual Media Service (VMS) is considered relevant for cultural heritage institutions and businesses for producing high-quality 3D models and other imagery for museums and heritage sites. The CNR-ISTI VCLab team and ICCU have presented the advanced VMS in a webinar to businesses and heritage institutions to explore existing demand and requirements for using the service.

Among the perceived “selling points” of the VMS are confidentiality, support of high-resolution interactive media, and the capability to link descriptive and narrative text to highlighted parts of a 3D model.

4.9 Use of services beyond research

The previous section addressed organisational users of ARIADNEplus services, such as cultural heritage institutions and businesses, who could use services for other purposes than archaeological research. This section addresses the end-users of services, such as citizen scientists.

4.9.1 Expectation and project approach

Programme expectation

[9] *“When applicable, the integrated and harmonised access to resources at European level can facilitate the use beyond research and contribute to evidence-based policy making.”*

Project approach

Serving various user groups beyond archaeological researchers and data managers (repositories, databases) is not a core objective of ARIADNEplus. The main intended user groups include also heritage managers and professionals in preventive archaeology, and others are addressed where appropriate.

For example, the project integrates information on metal-detector and other finds by amateurs in countries where this is permitted, and registration of finds in national databases has been enabled. Therefore, such amateurs are a very relevant user group of the ARIADNE portal. In general, however,

the portal can be used openly and freely by anybody interested in discovering and accessing available archaeological data, for example, educators and students for project work.

Policy-making for archaeological and cultural heritage is a complex matter due to conflicting interests, especially protection vs. exploitation, different implementation of international conventions and actual heritage management practices across countries (EAC 2018). Contributions to evidence-based policy making by researchers who use ARIADNEplus services and data may be possible, but this has not been defined as a core focus of the ARIADNE initiative in its current phase.

4.9.2 Selected end-users beyond research

The ARIADNEplus data portal can be openly and freely accessed and used by anybody. Thus, the portal, by making data of different providers available, not only for archaeological researchers and heritage management practitioners, but for all interested to discover, access and use available data, is a form of “public archaeology”. The project aims to go beyond this by addressing user groups likely to be interested in learning about archaeological artefacts and actively use the data portal.

ARIADNEplus integrates information on metal-detector and other finds by amateurs in countries where this is permitted and registration of finds in national databases has been enabled.⁶⁷ By bringing records from these databases into the ARIADNEplus portal, contributions of citizens to archaeology become visible also on the European level.

In turn, such “citizen scientists” (Dobat 2022) can use the portal to look for comparable finds or use it to investigate distribution patterns of finds. To support these purposes, extensive analysis of data records and testing of the portal for possible improvements has been carried out (ARIADNEplus 2022e).

Potential other users of the ARIADNEplus data portal are teachers and students interested in archaeology and cultural heritage. Access to data resources may stimulate study work and visits to archaeological museums and sites. For these groups, teaching and learning materials with worked examples are usually required to promote and support projects in schools or extracurricular activities. However, production and dissemination of such materials, necessary in different languages, was not a planned task with budget in the current phase of the ARIADNE initiative.

4.9.3 Summary of results

ARIADNEplus integrates information on metal-detector and other finds by amateurs in countries where this is permitted and registration of finds in national databases has been enabled. Therefore, such amateurs are a very relevant user group of the ARIADNE portal.

By bringing records from the finds databases into the ARIADNEplus portal, contributions of citizens to archaeology become visible also on the European level. In turn, such “citizen scientists” can use the portal to look for comparable finds or use it to investigate distribution patterns of finds.

Other groups likely to be interested in learning about archaeological sites and artefacts and actively use the data portal have been considered, particularly teachers and students. For this target group usually teaching and learning materials are required to promote and support projects in schools or extracurricular activities. However, production of such materials, necessary in different languages, was not possible in the current phase of the ARIADNE initiative.

⁶⁷ Information from Digitale Metaldektektorfund (DIME) in Denmark, provided by Aarhus University; FindSampo in Finland, provided by University of Helsinki for the Finnish Heritage Agency; Portable Antiquities of the Netherlands (PAN), provided by DANS, and Portable Antiquities Scheme (PAS), provided in kind by the British Museum.

4.10 TNA, training workshops and resources

This section addresses the Transnational Access (TNA) offer for researchers and data managers to visit ARIADNEplus competence centres, other training opportunities provided, and the ARIADNEplus online Training Hub.

4.10.1 Expectation and project approach

Programme expectation

[5] *“A new generation of researchers is educated that is ready to optimally exploit all the essential tools for their research.”*

Project approach

The programme expectation focuses on education (training) of researchers on using “essential tools” for their research. It remains unclear which tools the “new generation of researchers” would use specifically, but taking account of the Research Infrastructures (RI) context and new research policies, the set of tools (and related skills) would include those for digital and open science practices, for FAIR data and data management plans (DMP). Indeed, researchers will increasingly need RI services for data-intensive online research and, at the same time, are requested to acquire skills in data management and sharing, based on the FAIR data principles.

ARIADNEplus supports these requirements through the provision of advanced portal and other data-centred services, Transnational Access (TNA) to partner competence centres, guidelines on FAIR good practices for researchers and data managers, FAIR data and other training (e.g., expert workshops), and an online Data Management Plan (DMP) tool and templates. All these offers are of course tailored to researchers and data managers in archaeology and cultural heritage, with a focus on digital skills and practices.

4.10.2 Transnational Access (TNA)

The project included the opportunity to offer researchers and data managers Transnational Access (TNA) to ARIADNEplus competence centres as individual study and training visits or participation in a summer school at a centre. The themes offered by the three centres were “Data Stewardship” at ADS, “Mapping existing datasets to CIDOC CRM” at PIN, “Implementing Interoperability” and “Visual Media for the Documentation of Fieldwork and Artefacts” at CNR-ISTI.

The first TNA call was disseminated in September 2019 with visits by candidates at ADS and PIN planned for between January and June 2020. 16 applications were received and based on the result of the internal and external evaluation 13 applicants received offers. Unfortunately, only two beneficiaries were able to complete their TNA prior to the global COVID-19 pandemic and travel restrictions. The remaining candidates for TNA in 2020 have had their TNA places held for future attendance.

Planned summer schools at CNR in 2020 had to be cancelled and rescheduled for 2021, but no TNA call was issued due to continued insecurity. The TNA programme was resumed in 2022, with all training offered as four Summer Schools between May and July 2022.

A total of 37 TNA places were offered, 34 either transferring from 2020 or applying for the first time in 2022. Of these 32 attending the Summer Schools, two candidates had to renounce at short notice for personal reasons. TNA participants came from project partners, associates and a few external ones as well.

In summary, despite the impact of COVID-19, 34 researchers and data managers were still able to benefit from the ARIADNEplus TNA programme for their projects.

4.10.3 Training workshops

Partners reported 12 training workshops with a total of 476 participants, with participation ranging between 20 and 89. The main topics were open access publications and data, FAIR data principles, data management plans, data sharing and interoperability.

Small group workshops to train partners and associates in the use of the data provision tools have not been considered, while expert workshops on special topics (e.g., modelling of excavation data) are included in the reporting on the conferences and other events.

Until February 2020, the training workshops were held in-person, thereafter online and in 2022 both in-person and online. Eight of the workshops had international and four national participants. Eight of these workshops were organised by partners, and four partners contributed substantially to the programme.

The workshop with 89 participants was “Data Management Tools for Archaeologists” (29 March 2022, online), organised by DANS and PIN, which focused on the ARIADNEplus DMP tool and templates for archaeologists.

4.10.4 Training Hub

The Training Hub⁶⁸ was launched in January 2021 to support perceived training needs of the ARIADNEplus user community. The Hub is a content-rich training resource with materials selected specifically for archaeological researchers and data managers.

The nine topics of the Training Hub are: Applying open/the Fair Principles to archaeology, Defining and implementing a Data Management Plan (DMP), Metadata and vocabularies for archaeological datasets, Managing a digital repository of archaeological data, Managing datasets from large archaeological projects, Depositing project datasets in a digital repository, Working with Research Infrastructures, Data Science, Other Useful Sources.

Across the nine themes, the Hub comprises of 65 carefully selected web-accessible resources in English from different providers, ARIADNEplus partners, as well as others. The resources are in formats such as online courses, training modules (text & video), web articles with links to training resources, video presentations, downloadable tools and tutorials, freely accessible books and other materials. Most of the training resources are considered as introductory-level while others, e.g., under Data Science Skills, will require some basics in using software and programming.

In the period between January 2021 and November 2022 the Hub attracted 3,948 visitors, for a total of 11,586 pages viewed. The Hub has quite a high percentage of return visitors (27.3%).

4.10.5 Summary of results

Transnational Access (TNA)

The TNA programme enabled researchers and data managers to visit ARIADNEplus competence centres for individual study and training, or participation in a summer school at a centre. The themes offered by the three centres were “Data Stewardship” at ADS, “Mapping existing datasets to CIDOC

⁶⁸ ARIADNEplus: Training Hub, <http://www.training.ariadne-infrastructure.eu>

CRM” at PIN, “Implementing Interoperability” and “Visual Media for the Documentation of Fieldwork and Artefacts” at CNR-ISTI.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the TNA programme could not be implemented as planned. From the first call only 2 of 13 beneficiaries were able to complete their TNA prior to the travel restrictions. Due to continued insecurity no further calls were issued in 2020 and 2021.

The TNA programme was resumed in 2022, with all training offered as four summer schools between May and July 2022, for a total of 32 participants.

Training workshops

Partners reported 12 larger training workshops with a total of 476 participants. The main topics were open access publications and data, FAIR data principles, data management plans, data sharing and interoperability. Eight of the workshops had international and four national participants. Eight of these workshops were organised by partners, and four partners contributed substantially to the programme.

Training Hub

The Training Hub, launched in January 2021, is a content-rich site of training resources selected specifically for archaeological researchers and data managers. The topics have been chosen to support perceived training needs of the ARIADNEplus user community. Across the nine topics, the Hub comprises of 65 web-accessible resources in English of different providers, ARIADNEplus partners, as well as others. In the period between January 2021 and November 2022, the Hub attracted 3,948 visitors, for a total of 11,586 pages viewed. The Hub has quite a high percentage of return visitors (27.3%).

4.11 Dissemination and communication

4.11.1 Expectation and project approach

RI Programme expectation

[6] *“Closer interactions between larger number of researchers active in and around a number of infrastructures facilitate cross-disciplinary fertilisations and a wider sharing of information, knowledge and technologies across fields and between academia and industry.”*

Dissemination and communication of ARIADNEplus supports the sharing of information and knowledge, albeit not “in and around” physical research infrastructures (e.g., laboratories) but through promoting the e-Infrastructure, services and shared data in conferences and workshops, publications, and broader dissemination through website articles and social media.

ARIADNEplus approach

The ARIADNEplus dissemination and communication activities support the outreach to, and involvement of, the archaeological research and data management community. This section summarises and highlights results regarding publications, conferences and other events, and the project website and Twitter channel. Results of training workshops are reported in [Section 4.10.3](#)).

4.11.2 Publications

Since project start in January 2019, partners and associates have published 53 ARIADNEplus related academic publications in journals, conference proceedings, edited volumes, etc. Of these, 45 have been published open access or as a preprint version available in an open access repository.

The publications include the 17 chapters of the open access book “The ARIADNE Impact” (Richards & Niccolucci 2019), published by Archeolingua. Since 7 October 2019, there have been 1,590 unique downloads of the book from the Zenodo repository.⁶⁹

Two data papers deserve a special mention: “An Aegean History and Archaeology Written through Radiocarbon Dates” by Katsianis et al. (2020) in the *Journal of Open Archaeology Data* describes an open access published dataset of radiocarbon dates for Aegean history and archaeology, a total of 3159 radiocarbon samples from 353 sites. It is the largest collection so far of such data from Greece. A data record of this collection is included in the ARIADNEplus portal.⁷⁰

“Deep Data Example: Zbiva, Early Medieval Data Set for the Eastern Alps Research” by Štular & Belak (2022) in the *Data Journal for the Humanities and Social Sciences* describes the Zbiva open access research database, the product of four decades of data collection and curation. 8,775 records from the database are included in the ARIADNE portal.⁷¹

Two special issues of open access ARIADNEplus papers are already planned for 2023, the first in *Internet Archaeology*, the second in Spanish in the *Revista del Museo de Antropología*, Argentina. The aim of this special issue is to disseminate in Latin America knowledge acquired by ARIADNEplus.

4.11.3 Conferences and other events

The ARIADNEplus partners and associates reported 88 conferences and various other events which they have (co-)organised (42) or attended to give ARIADNE-related presentations and network with participants. Training workshops are not included here (see [Section 4.10.3](#)).

The reported total number of participants of the conference sessions, round tables etc. and other events is 4,077, with on average of 46 participants per event. 61 events had international and 27 national participants. Due to the COVID-19 crisis, most events were held online.

The largest participation of around 300 participants was achieved during the online conference “3D Digital Cultural Heritage for Resilience, Recovery and Sustainability” (27 May 2020, European Commission 2020b), which ARIADNEplus and Inception s.r.l. (a creative business start-up company) organised in collaboration with the European Commission, DG CONNECT; the conference was live-streamed on YouTube and the content on YouTube also got nearly 2,800 views thereafter.

4.11.4 Website access

The website access is monitored via Google Analytics. In the period from January 2019 to November 2022, the website attracted about 30,000 visitors, for a total of over 86,000 pages viewed. There has been a steady rate of visitors, between 500-1000 per month, with around 14% being return visitors.

⁶⁹ <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3476712>

⁷⁰ <https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/search?q=&publisher=University%20of%20Patras>

⁷¹ <https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/publisher/zrc?publisher=ZRC%20SAZU>

Figure 10: Website access statistics, January 2019 to November 2022.

In the 11 months from January to November 2022 there have been about 8,600 visitors (23,861 page views), hence more than in the previous years (see also the user flow chart below).

Analysing the acquisition channels leading users to the ARIADNEplus website, direct traffic stands at 41.8%, search engine results pages (“Organic Search”) at 37.7%, sites that “referred” visitors to the website by clicking a link at 14.2%, and social media platforms at 6.3%.

Figure 11: Website traffic by source: acquisition channels.

4.11.5 Twitter

Twitter is being used regularly by the project to bring attention to outputs, notify users of events of interest, and retweet items of interest.

At the end of the ARIADNE project, the Twitter account @ARIADNE_Network had about 900 followers, with a few additions until its reactivation as @ARIADNEplus at the end of January 2019. Until the beginning of December 2022, the number of followers grew to 2,082.

In the last year, the project sent 34 Tweets which received a total of 73,177 views. The most popular Tweet during this period, with 9,557 views, was the announcement in 2020 that 38,000 fieldwork reports from INRAP had been published on the ARIADNE portal.

4.11.6 Summary of results

Publications

Since the start of the project in January 2019, partners and associates have published 53 ARIADNEplus related academic publications in journals, conference proceedings, edited volumes, etc. Of these, 45 have been published open access or as a preprint version available in an open access repository.

The publications include the 17 chapters of the open access book “The ARIADNE Impact” (Richards & Niccolucci 2019), published by Archeolingua. Since 7 October 2019, there were 1,590 unique downloads of the book from the Zenodo repository.

Two special issues of open access ARIADNEplus papers are already planned for 2023, the first in *Internet Archaeology*, the second in Spanish in the *Revista del Museo de Antropología*, Argentina. The aim of this special issue is to disseminate in Latin America knowledge acquired by ARIADNEplus.

Conferences and other events

The ARIADNEplus partners and associates reported 88 conference sessions and other events which they have (co-)organised (42) or attended to give ARIADNE-related presentations and network with participants. The training workshops are not included here.

The total number of reported attendants of the presentations is 4,077, on average 46 per event. 61 events had international, and 27 national participants. Due to the COVID-19 crisis, most events were held online.

Project website and Twitter

The ARIADNEplus website informs visitors about the project’s goals, community network, workshops, training and TNA, news & events. In the period from January 2019 to November 2022 the website attracted about 30,000 visitors, for a total of over 86,000 pages viewed. There has been a steady rate of visitors, between 500-1000 per month, with around 14% being return visitors.

The project’s Twitter channel has been used regularly to bring attention to project activities and results; in the last year, the project sent 34 Tweets which received a total of 73,177 views. The channel was reactivated at the end of January 2019 with 900 followers of the original ARIADNE project. At the beginning of December 2022, the number of followers has grown to nearly 2,100.

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